

Faculté des géosciences et de l'environnement
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RECONSTRUCTING CLIMATE PATTERNS IN EUROPE
DURING THE LGM FROM INVERSIONS OF PAST ICE
EXTENTS

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VJERAN VIŠNJEVIĆ

Master Physique-Géophysique de l'Université de Zagreb, Croatie
de l'Université Zagreb, Croatia

Jury

Prof. Dr. Christian Kull	Université de Lausanne	Président du jury
Prof. Dr. Frédéric Herman	Université de Lausanne	Directeur de thèse
Prof. Dr. Yury Podladchikov	Université de Lausanne	Expert interne
Prof. Dr. Jean Braun	GFZ Potsdam, Germany	Expert externe
Dr. Guillaume Jovet	ETH Zurich, Switzerland	Expert externe

Lausanne, 2019

In memory of my grandmother.

"We find our path by walking it"
Maya Angelou

"Not all those who wander are lost"
JRR Tolkien

Synopsis

Le dernier maximum glaciaire (LGM), 26 à 19 ka, représente la dernière phase froide la plus récente de l'histoire de la Terre et la dernière fois que le climat des planètes était très différent de celui d'aujourd'hui. Cette dernière avancée glaciaire était un événement mondial et couvrait à la fois les hémisphères Nord et Sud. En Amérique du Nord, les calottes de glace Laurentide et Cordillère couvraient le nord du continent, les rivières Missouri et Ohio jusqu'à Manhattan, tandis qu'en Europe, la calotte British Island et la calotte Fenoscandinavian couvraient la majeure partie du nord atteignant le centre de l'Allemagne, entraînant les conditions climatiques froides et sèches pendant le LGM en Europe centrale et occidentale et la création de calottes glaciaires à travers les Alpes et les Pyrénées. Afin de comprendre les conditions climatiques pendant le LGM, il est nécessaire de connaître l'évolution de la température et des précipitations depuis aujourd'hui, ainsi que le degré de modification des directions dominantes de la circulation atmosphérique par rapport à aujourd'hui.

Le LGM représente une expansion glaciaire, qui a globalement laissé une empreinte observable forte sur le paysage sous la forme de moraines, de lignes de coupe et d'autres caractéristiques géomorphologiques glaciaires. Ces caractéristiques reflètent l'étendue des anciens glaciers et des anciennes calottes glaciaires, qui fournissent à leur tour des informations sur la température et les conditions de précipitations passées. Je présenterai ici une méthode qui utilise des caractéristiques géomorphologiques telles que l'étendue et l'épaisseur de la glace, et la combine avec une modélisation de l'écoulement de la glace pour étudier les modèles de climat et la circulation atmosphérique régionale en Europe au cours de la LGM. J'ai appliqué cette approche récemment développée pour étudier les régimes climatiques dans les Alpes et les Pyrénées, car les deux chaînes de montagnes sont influencées par la même circulation atmosphérique régionale. Les résultats présentés reconstituent une forte influence zonale en Europe, sous la forme d'un fort changement de précipitation W-E sur les Alpes et d'un changement N-S sur les Pyrénées, faisant de l'Atlantique la principale source d'humidité. Deuxièmement, les résultats de la reconstruction ont été utilisés pour limiter les variations de température et de précipitation pendant le LGM et ont permis de constater que les Alpes se situaient en moyenne (annuelle) autour de 9°C environ dans les Pyrénées et de °C environ plus froid qu'aujourd'hui.

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Abstract

Over 20 ky ago, Earth experienced its last large scale glacial advance. Ice sheets and ice caps covered large areas in both the Northern and the Southern Hemisphere. Conditions over Europe were cold and dry, with both the Scandinavian Peninsula and the British Isles in the north, as well as the Alps and the Pyrenees in central and western Europe, covered by ice. The influence of these ice sheets and ice caps on the atmospheric circulation, and to what point did the ice sheets in the north, and the subsequent expansion of the polar front, control the position of the Westerly winds and the regional precipitation patterns over Europe, remains a topic of debate. Secondly, there is a strong need for additional constraints on the amplitudes of mean temperature and precipitation changes compared to present-day. Although there is a discrepancy between observations and the modeling studies on both issues, it is clear that proper representation of ice surface topography in the models will strongly effect on the outcomes of such paleoclimate reconstructions. The approach presented in this study will be to combine ice flow modeling with the geomorphological evidence these ice caps and ice sheets left in the landscape in the form of moraines and trimlines. This approach enables us to gain insights into past climate conditions, by constraining changes and exploring patterns in temperature and precipitation across a mountain range, thus recovering valuable information on the regional atmospheric circulation over Europe.

In order to investigate these questions, I have developed an inverse method to reconstruct the spatially variable mass balance rate of an ice cap, and in return the spatially variable position of the Equilibrium line altitude (ELA), using mapped ice extent and ice thickness data as input. The method is applied to the mountain ranges of the Alps and the Pyrenees, as they are effected by the same regional climate, and the recovered spatial variability in the patterns of the ELA reflects patterns in temperature and precipitation, indicating to the dominant directions of the regional atmospheric circulation. Since inverting ice extent data does not lead to the unique solution, I ran many scenarios with different climatic forcing in order to investigate the parameter space of the problem. In the case of the Alps, all of the presented scenarios recover a clear W-E gradient in the position of the ELA across the mountain range, and a N-S gradient in the west and central part, pointing to a dominantly zonal circulation with Westerlies bringing moisture from the Atlantic. This is supported by the Pyrenees reconstruction, where the method recovers a clear N-S gradient for all scenarios, indicating that the moisture source from the direction of the Atlantic.

Finally, I used the change between present day ELA and the recovered LGM one to constrain mean annual temperature and precipitation change. I find that the temperature differences were about 9°C in the Alps and 6°C in the Pyrenees, and that climate must have been at least 25% drier in order to reproduce temperature depressions reported by proxy studies (pollen). The presented results show that by using the newly developed approach one can reconstruct

valuable paleoclimatic information by using only ice flow modeling and mapped ice extents, enabling the applicability of the method even to areas where the data coverage is sparse.

Résumé

Le dernier maximum glaciaire (LGM), 26 à 19 ka, représente la dernière phase froide la plus récente de l'histoire de la Terre et la dernière fois que le climat des planètes était très différent de celui d'aujourd'hui. Cette dernière avancée glaciaire était un événement mondial et couvrait à la fois les hémisphères Nord et Sud. En Amérique du Nord, les calottes de glace Laurentide et Cordillère couvraient le nord du continent, les rivières Missouri et Ohio jusqu'à Manhattan, tandis qu'en Europe, la calotte British Island et la calotte Fenoscandinavian couvraient la majeure partie du nord atteignant le centre de l'Allemagne, entraînant les conditions climatiques froides et sèches pendant le LGM en Europe centrale et occidentale et la création de calottes glaciaires à travers les Alpes et les Pyrénées. Afin de comprendre les conditions climatiques pendant le LGM, il est nécessaire de connaître l'évolution de la température et des précipitations depuis aujourd'hui, ainsi que le degré de modification des directions dominantes de la circulation atmosphérique par rapport à aujourd'hui.

LGM représente une expansion glaciaire, qui a globalement laissé une empreinte observable forte sur le paysage sous la forme de moraines, de lignes de coupe et d'autres caractéristiques géomorphologiques glaciaires. Ces caractéristiques reflètent l'étendue des anciens glaciers et des anciennes calottes glaciaires, qui fournissent à leur tour des informations sur la température et les conditions de précipitations passées. Je présenterai ici une méthode qui utilise des caractéristiques géomorphologiques telles que l'étendue et l'épaisseur de la glace, et la combine avec une modélisation de l'écoulement de la glace pour étudier les modèles de climat et la circulation atmosphérique régionale en Europe au cours de la LGM. J'ai appliqué cette approche récemment développée pour étudier les régimes climatiques dans les Alpes et les Pyrénées, car les deux chaînes de montagnes sont influencées par la même circulation atmosphérique régionale. Les résultats présentés reconstituent une forte influence zonale en Europe, sous la forme d'un fort changement de précipitation W-E sur les Alpes et d'un changement N-S sur les Pyrénées, faisant de l'Atlantique la principale source d'humidité. Deuxièmement, les résultats de la reconstruction ont été utilisés pour limiter les variations de température et de précipitation pendant le LGM et ont permis de constater que les Alpes se situaient en moyenne (annuelle) autour de 9°C environ dans les Pyrénées et de 6°C environ plus froid qu'aujourd'hui.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Due to increasing warming of the Earth's system in recent decades, our planet is experiencing dynamic changes in global climate. Evidence and effects of this warming have been found in almost every branch of geoscience and are already influencing Earth surface processes and feedbacks across scales. Tackling the broad range of these effects, from the rise of sea level around heavily populated coasts caused by the melting of glaciers and ice sheets around the world to local changes in climate and soil chemistry endangering agriculture as we know it, probably presents the largest challenge of this civilization for present and future. The latest report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) stated potential global mean surface temperature warming up to 4°C assuming emissions that continue to rise throughout the 21st century (scenario RCP 8.5, IPCC 2014), a value comparable to the estimated temperature cooling between the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) and present-day. In order to improve our models and reduce uncertainties in our future projections, to better understand the potential effect a worldwide 4°C change in temperature can have, it is important to inform the predictions of future evolution with the documented evolution of the past. In that context, paleo reconstructions give us the opportunity to compare our model outputs with proxy data and observations, to constrain initial conditions for future projections, and to gain insight into periods when our planet was unlike the one today.

The Quaternary period represents the most recent Ice Age, spanning over the last 2.6 million years of Earth's history dominated by the cyclical interchange between long and cold glacial, and short and warm interglacial periods. These glacial and interglacial periods are defined by the expansion (glacial) and retreat (interglacial) of ice sheets in the northern and southern

hemisphere, following the Milanković cycles. The LGM (26-19 ka), part of the Last glacial period spanning from the Eemian interglacial (113 ka) until the Younger Dryas (11 ka), represents the last time the world's ice sheets reached their maximum extent, and is followed by the current warm interglacial period. Although the Quaternary period experienced repeated Glacial-Interglacials, the LGM is the best documented glaciation as it overprinted the former ones, and is thus chosen to be the focus of this thesis. The LGMs extensive glaciation left a strong imprint on present day landscape. We observe numerous conspicuous features such as U-shaped valleys, terminal moraines, trimlines, drumlins, isostatic rebound and other geomorphological features. Combining these observations with tectonic and paleoclimatic proxies to constrain atmospheric, ocean, glacial and vegetation models enables us to constrain past climate changes and the evolution of the landscape.

1.1 LGM climate

During the LGM our planet was extensively glaciated and climate was vastly different than today (Annan et al. 2013). Earth's surface was covered with large ice sheets and ice caps on both hemispheres. In North America the Laurentide and the Cordilleran ice sheets, together with the Greenland ice sheet, covered the north of the continent reaching south down to Missouri and Ohio Rivers all the way to Manhattan in the east. In Europe, the British Islands and Fenoscandinavian Ice Sheet covered most of northern Europe reaching down to Berlin, while the Alpine ice cap stood in the center of Europe, locally pinned to its mountain range. The Southern Hemisphere glaciation was dominated by the West and East Antarctica Ice Sheets, while the Patagonian Ice Sheet and the Southern Alps ice cap covered the mountain ranges of South America and New Zealand (Clark et al. 2009). The presence of these large glaciated areas in both hemispheres lead to a globally 4°C colder world than today (Annan et al. 2013), but also expanded the position of the polar front on the poles, influencing global and regional circulations (Florineth and Schlüchter 2000).

In the case of Europe, there is a disagreement between model reconstructions and proxy data (e.g. pollen, Jost et al. 2005; Wu et al. 2007). The pollen studies show that the LGM was colder, $12\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ north of the Alps - Pyrenees line and $10\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ south of that line, and drier with precipitation north of the Mediterranean reduced by $60\pm 20\%$ (Peyron et al. 1998; Tarasov et al. 1999). At the same time, Beyerle et al. (1998) used a multitracer study in northern Switzerland and reported a cooling of at least 5°C . On the modeling side, the atmospheric models underestimate the LGM cooling over Europe, especially in winter (Jost et al. 2005) and western Europe (Kageyama et al. 2006). Both the results of the Paleoclimate Modeling Intercomparison Project (PMIP2, Braconnot et al. 2007) and a study using a fully coupled atmosphere-ocean general circulation model report an annual average cooling of $5\text{-}10^{\circ}\text{C}$ over ice free Europe, and up to 40°C colder over the ice sheet in winter (Braconnot et al. 2007).

Strandberg et al. (2011). Studies using ice flow models have recovered a drier climate during the LGM with temperature depressions of 8-15°C (Heyman et al. 2013), depending on the reduction of precipitation (25-75%), while Allen et al. (2008b) recovered mean temperature anomalies of $15\pm 0.3^\circ\text{C}$ north of the Alps and $13\pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ in the Mediterranean region, assuming a 40% reduction in precipitation. The cause for significant discrepancies reported between pollen reconstructions and models lies in the difficulty to account for the influence of temporal changes in the concentration of atmospheric CO_2 while reconstructing pollen, as well as the lack of modern analogs for some fossil pollen assemblages (Ramstein et al. 2007; Wu et al. 2007). Models, on the other hand, struggle with the choice of initial conditions and the difficulty to include all of the feedbacks between ocean, atmosphere, ice and vegetation in their simulations, as well as the rising computational demands such models have in order to simulate grid sizes small enough to simulate spatial variability as well as the effect of surface topography on regional atmospheric circulation (Jost et al. 2005; Ramstein et al. 2007; Pausata et al. 2011).

To understand the climate in Europe during the LGM one must investigate the influence of North Hemisphere ice sheets (Laurentide, Cordilleran, Greenland, British Islands and Fenoscandinavian Ice Sheets) and ice caps (Alps and the Pyrenees) on the wind and precipitation patterns. Florineth and Schlüchter (2000) proposed that glaciations in the Northern Hemisphere lead to the expansion of the polar front, the southward shifting of the associated storm track and the Westerly winds. Evidence for this comes from the existence of three large ice domes over the Alps south of the weather divide, reconstructed by glacio-geological mapping and indicating a dominant southerly atmospheric circulation. The southward shift strongly changed the regional circulation by bringing moisture to Europe and the Alps from the Mediterranean Sea (Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000). This hypothesis has been reaffirmed by Luetscher et al. (2015) in a speleothem study, as well as Monegato et al. (2017) where the authors use new stratigraphic and chronologic constraints from the Garda morainic amphitheater to propose separation of the LGM into two phases; 26-24 ka and 23-17 ka. The first phase corresponds to the period of growth of the North American Ice Sheet (NAIS), and the expansion of the polar front shifting the Westerlies south. This resulted in a very dry central and north Europe, while the moisture supply for the Alps came from the south. The second phase corresponds to the withdrawal of the NAIS, northward retreat of the polar front and return of the Westerlies to their present-day position. The authors argue that this shift lead to the beginning of the retreat for the Alpine glaciers, by increasing precipitation over central and north Europe and feeding the British Islands and Fenoscandinavian ice sheets with moisture. Kuhlemann et al. (2008) found the LGM patterns to be amplified but analogous to the conditions during the Little Ice Age (LIA), and proposed a seasonal alternation between meridional circulation during cold seasons, and zonal circulation during warm seasons.

The proposed shift of the Westerlies was also investigated using atmospheric models, coupled with oceanic models of different degrees of complexity, as well as glacial modeling. The main conclusion drawn from atmospheric models is that the atmospheric circulation over the Atlantic, and the position of the storm-track, strongly depends on the parametrization of ice surface topography of the North Hemisphere ice sheets (Riviere 2010; Pausata et al., 2011), thus emphasizing the need and importance for a precise reconstruction of the LGM ice sheets. While Lainé et al. (2009) observe a southeastward extension of the storm-track, Riviere (2010) finds that the LGM exhibits much less latitudinal fluctuations of the eddy-driven jets than the pre-industrial period and that the latitudinal shifts of the eddy-driven jets from one phase to another are much weaker, and resemble more to pulses than oscillations. Similarly, Li and Battisti (2008) used a fully coupled global climate model to simulate strong and more zonally oriented steady atmospheric jets in the Atlantic with reduced storminess, combined with weak transient eddy activity compared to present-day. The authors explain the discrepancies between their reconstruction and the ones simulating conditions more similar to present day due to the differences in the ice sheet topography and sea surface conditions between models.

On the other hand, glacial modeling offers another approach to constrain this problem. Since ice caps reflect climate, analysing how their response to external forcing changes spatially gives us information about the spatial variability of that climatic forcing at a regional scale. Heyman et al. (2013) used an ice flow model to reconstruct the mapped LGM glacier extents from smaller mountain ranges north of the Alps in France, Germany and Czech Republic and concluded a need for a strong west-east gradient in temperature, with cooler conditions in the west. This conclusion differs from the one by Becker et al. (2016), where an ice flow model was used to reconstruct the ice extent over the Alps during the LGM using the present-day precipitation pattern. These authors concluded that in order to reproduce the mapped ice extent it is necessary to halve the amount of precipitation north of the weather divide, attributing this to the consequence of the southward shift of the Westerlies. Becker et al. (2016) assumed climatic steady state conditions, supposing that the ice reached its mapped maximum extent everywhere at the same time. This study was followed by the work of Seguinot et al. (2018), where the authors modeled a transient simulation of the Alps during the whole Last Glacial Period. The authors concluded that there is no need for the north-south gradient in precipitation, due to the transient nature of the LGM climate in their simulation, and emphasized the need for a west-east gradient in precipitation or temperature in order to reproduce observations.

derestimating ice thickness. The issues with modeling studies lie in the difficulty to properly simulate LGM regional climate over Europe, the unconstrained spatial variations in timing of the ice reaching its maximum extent, the unknown differences between present-day and LGM bedrock, and the parametrization of the ice flow.

The conditions over the Pyrenees during the LGM are less known. [González-Sampériz et al. \(2006\)](#) performed palynological, sedimentological and stable isotopic analyses to reconstruct the paleoclimatic evolution and vegetation history in the Central-Western Pyrenean Range for the last 30 kyr. Their findings confirmed that the Pyrenees experienced a previous deglaciation before 30 ka ([García-Ruiz et al. 2000](#); [González-Sampériz et al. 2006](#); [Delmas 2015](#); [Palacios et al. 2015](#)), as well as the glacial re-advance corresponding to the global LGM. Their conclusion is that short-term variability from high latitudes drove the climate evolution of the central-western Spanish Pyrenees during the last 30 ka from northern Atlantic regions to the Iberian Peninsula. They assume that the main transfer mechanisms for this forcing were instantaneous: mainly cold and drier northwesterly winds, the colder sea surface temperature (SST) entering through the Strait of Gibraltar, or meltwater pulses originating from the Scandinavian Ice Sheet ([González-Sampériz et al. 2006](#)).

Glaciologists have been developing methods, using area accumulation ratio (AAR) or ice flow models, to reproduce geomorphological features (terminal moraines, trimlines), reconstruct the ice surface and gain information about the paleo atmospheric conditions encoded in the landscape ([Porter 1975](#); [Zuo and Oerlemans 1997](#); [Plummer and Phillips 2003](#); [Anderson and others 2006](#); [Kessler et al. 2006](#); [Allen et al. 2008b](#); [Jouvet et al. 2008](#); [Golledge et al. 2012](#); [Heyman et al. 2013](#); [Rowan et al. 2014](#); [Eaves et al. 2016](#); [Mey et al. 2016](#); [Mackintosh et al. 2017](#)). The difficulty with these approaches is in the fact that reconstructing the mapped ice extent does not lead to a unique solution, as many ice surfaces can fit into the same ice extent under various climate conditions. This problem could be better constrained by adding more data, such as ice thickness, but they are often unavailable or unreliable, as in the case of the Alps.

A key unknown in glacier-based paleo reconstructions is the mass balance rate of a glacier or an ice cap. The mass balance rate is the annual gain or loss of mass on a glacier ([Oerlemans 2001](#); [Cuffey and Paterson 2010](#)), and as a function of precipitation and temperature defines ablation and accumulation areas. The altitude at which the mass balance rate of a glacier or an ice cap equals zero is called the Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA). The position of the ELA can be assumed constant for a single glacier under steady climate, but for a large mountain range it is spatially variable, reflecting regional atmospheric circulation. Changes in the position of the ELA are coupled with changes in temperature and precipitation ([Kuhn 1989](#); [Ohmura et al. 1992](#); [Kerschner et al. 2000](#)), and if one knows temperature or precipitation it is possible to constrain the other, thus gaining valuable information about the climate ([Kerschner et al. 2000](#)). Widely used methods like AAR use glacier outlines and a predetermined ratio between

the accumulation area of a glacier and its whole area. The AAR method assumes a constant accumulation area ratio and requires knowledge of the ice surface, which is often unknown for paleo glaciers, leading to potentially large errors in the reconstruction (Kessler et al., 2006; Mackintosh et al., 2017). Ice flow modeling avoids this problem because there are no a priori assumptions on the ice surface, the ice extent or the accumulation area ratio. In order to use an ice flow model to reproduce observation, it is important to choose, an appropriate mass balance model ice flow approximation. There is a range of existing models used in glacial history reconstructions to simulate climate (Kessler et al., 2006; Golledge et al., 2012; Becker et al., 2016; Seguinot et al., 2018), from simple linear approximation (Kessler et al., 2006; Oerlemans et al., 2011) and positive degree-day models (Braithwaite, 1995; Allen et al., 2008a; Heyman et al., 2013), to sophisticated energy balance mass balance models (Oerlemans, 1992, 1997; Becker et al., 2016). The increase in complexity of the mass balance models used usually follows the increase in the number of unknown parameters, all of which vary during a glacial cycle and are difficult to constrain for paleo reconstructions. Additionally, high number of unknown parameters makes full exploration of the parameter space computationally very expensive, and can lead to many possible parameter combinations for the same solution.

Similarly, a range of ice flow models of various complexity have been used for glacial history and paleoclimatic reconstruction studies. Starting from simpler approaches using the Shallow ice approximation (SIA) (Hutter, 1983), a zero-order model, hybrid models (Bueller et al., 2009; Pollard and DeConto, 2009), higher order models (Blatter, 1995; Pattyn, 2003) to using Full-Stokes models (Gagliardini et al., 2013), solving the full set of momentum equations. Although Full-Stokes models are capable of fully simulating ice dynamics, and are considered to be the most accurate, they are still computationally too expensive for large-scale paleo simulations and are replaced with approximations of the Full-Stokes model in such studies.

The proper choice of complexity of ice flow models used for paleoclimatic studies is a topic of debate. Parallel Ice Sheet Model (PISM), a hybrid model, has been widely used for paleoclimatic reconstructions, specially to reconstruct the European and Southern Alps during the LGM (Golledge et al., 2012; Becker et al., 2016; Seguinot et al., 2018), while Plach et al. (2018) used a higher order Ice Sheet System Model (ISSM) to model Greenland throughout the Eemian period. A detailed discussion on the use of ice flow models of different levels of complexity can be found in Furst et al. (2013) and Kirchner et al. (2016). Kirchner et al. (2016) propose a newly developed ISCAL model (Ahlkrona et al., 2016), combining the Shallow Ice Approximation and with Full-stokes equations and matching the accuracy standards of the Full Stokes model, to replace hybrid models for paleo reconstructions on the timescales of tens of thousands of years. On the other hand, recent studies on Greenland (Furst et al., 2013; Zekollari et al., 2017; Plach et al., 2018) compare SIA models with higher order ones and conclude that the surface mass balance forcing and the boundary conditions are more important than the representation of ice flow (Zekollari et al., 2017; Plach et al., 2018), stating

that for future projections the largest source of uncertainties arises from climatic projections rather than the complexity of ice-dynamics (Furst et al., 2013, 2015). Zekollari et al. (2017), emphasize the fact that the inclusion of the higher order stresses, as well as higher spatial resolution (from 500 m to 250 m), is of limited added value, claiming that the added effect is smaller than the uncertainties related to the model setup.

1.3 Objectives of the Phd thesis

The primary objective of this PhD is to address of these issues by:

- 1. developing a new inversion method to reconstruct past climate from observed ice extents and**
- 2. applying the developed method to reconstruct LGM climate conditions in Europe.**

In order to explore and reconstruct the spatial variability of climate forcing across a mountain range I have developed an inverse method to reconstruct the position of the spatially variable ELA, and in return the mass balance rate, over a mountain chain using an ice flow model (Višnjević et al., 2018). The pattern of spatial variations in the ELA gives us insight into variations in temperature and precipitations fields over the mountain range, pointing to the dominating directions of the regional atmospheric circulation. The method is based on Tikhonov regularization (Tikhonov, 1963; Poplavskii et al., 2001), assuming a smooth solution, and consist of iteratively running the ice flow model, comparing the calculated ice extent from the model with the mapped one and updating the ELA for the next iteration, until we reach a good fit with data. As shown in Višnjević et al. (2018), the method can use ice extent and ice thickness data as model constraints, but because of aforementioned discrepancies between ice thickness reconstructions and modeling studies I have decided to use only mapped ice extent data. The main advantage this new method brings to the field is its capability to recover spatial variations on the scale of a mountain range.

To converge to a solution of the inverse problem, at the moment it is necessary to compute up to a 1000 inverse model iterations, each calculating the evolution of an ice flow model until steady state. To do so, a fast ice flow model is needed. In this study I wrote an ice flow model based on Shallow Ice Approximation (SIA), with the addition of flexural isostasy (Watts, 2001), a flux limiter to avoid unrealistically large fluxes that can occur when using SIA models on high resolutions, a constriction factor to account for the effect of lateral drag not included in SIA (Braun et al., 1999; Herman and Braun, 2008; Egholm et al., 2011), as well as the simple approach to mimic frozen bed conditions by reducing sliding in places

where the basal temperature is below zero. The model is described in Chapter 1 (Višnjević et al., 2018).

Because the method requires a lot of iterations on high resolution, it is necessary to develop a fast code. For that reason, the ice flow model is written to run on Graphic Processing Units (GPUs) using Cuda C platform. Due to their structure and purpose (graphic rendering) within the computer architecture, devoting more transistors to data processing than data catching and flow control, GPUs are specialized for intensive high parallel computing (NVIDIA, 2017). The CUDA structure of grids, blocks and threads ultimately enables for each point of the domain to be calculated simultaneously (one point - one thread), thus drastically increasing time needed to solve the desired system of equation. The local nature of the equations I am solving, mostly local derivations in diffusion equations, requires each cell to access memory only in the neighbouring cells, and combined with a large number of threads each GPU has allows me to apply my method to large regions using high resolutions. This makes them ideal for computing large-scale parallel problems such as ours.

To recover the climate patterns in central Europe during the LGM I have developed, tested and verified the method to reconstruct spatially variable ELA (Chapter 1) and applied it to the Alps (Chapter 2) and the Pyrenees (Chapter 3), because both of the mountain ranges are affected by the same regional circulation, thus a combined analysis gives us a better insight into the system. Using the method, I can reconstruct the spatially variable position of the ELA with the recovered patterns and gradients reflecting the influences of atmospheric circulation though effects of temperature and precipitation on its position. As stated above, inverting ice extent will not result in a unique solution, so the inversion is calculated for a range of different climate scenarios, as well as scenarios where the dominant ice flow and inverse model parameters are varied (Chapter 2). Then for each reconstructed scenario I calculate a change in the ELA between present day and the LGM. This change in the position of the ELA is translated for each scenario into a change in temperature (Chapter 3), using a simple temperature-ELA relation from Kuhlemann et al. (2008), thus enabling us to further constrain our result by comparing the reconstructed scenarios with proxy data.

The presented method enables us to investigate the spatial variability and constrain the temperature change of past climate on a regional scale. Since the method only requires mapped ice extent as input, this approach gives us the opportunity to investigate atmospheric circulations and gain valuable insights on temperature and precipitation in areas of the world, and points in time, where data coverage is sparse.

The thesis is organized in three chapters:

1. Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modeling

2. Climatic patterns over the European Alps during the LGM derived from inversion of the paleo-ice extent
3. Constraining temperature and precipitation changes during the Last Glacial Maximum in Europe from past ice extents

The thesis is summarized in 3 papers. The first one is published in *Journal of Glaciology* (Višnjević et al., 2018). The second is currently in revision in *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, and the third one in *Geology*.

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CHAPTER 2

Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modeling

Vjeran Višnjević¹, Frédéric Herman¹, Yury Podladchikov²

¹Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne

²Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Lausanne

Abstract

With the conclusion of the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), about 20 000 years ago, ended the most recent long-lasting cold phase in Earth history. This last glacial advance left a strong observable imprint on the landscape, such as moraines, trimlines and other glacial geomorphic features. These features reflect the extent of former glaciers and ice caps, which in turn provides information on past temperature and precipitation conditions. Here we present an inverse approach to reconstruct the equilibrium line altitudes (E) from observed ice extents. The ice flow model is developed solving the mass conservation equation using the shallow ice approximation (SIA) and implemented using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs). We present the theoretical basis of the inversion method, which relies on a Tikhonov regularization, and demonstrate its ability to constrain spatial variations in mass balance with idealized and real glaciers.

2.1 Introduction

The Quaternary period, spanning the last 2.6 million years of Earth history, was marked by warm and short interludes between long and cold periods. While literature provides tight constraints on how climate varied during glacial periods in marine settings (Zachos et al., 2001; Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005; Herbert and others, 2016), changes in temperature and precipitation on continents remain poorly constrained. Use and availability of proxies such as pollen (Peyron et al., 1998) and speleothems (Luetscher et al., 2015) can help shed more light on past climate conditions. However, past glacial advances have left a strong imprint on the Earth's surface in the form of moraines, trimlines and other glacial geomorphic features, which provide us invaluable information on past climate on continents (Penck, 1905; Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Laabs and Carson, 2005). Furthermore, thanks to geochronological methods (Gosse and Phillips, 2001), such as ^{14}C (Hajdas, 2009), cosmogenic nuclide (Blanckenburg and Willenbring, 2014) and optically stimulated luminescence dating (Rhodes, 2011), the timing of past glacial advances can be dated.

Ice flow models have been used before to infer past climate conditions on continents (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Anderson and others, 2006; Kessler et al., 2006; Juvet et al., 2008; Gолledge et al., 2012; Rowan et al., 2014; Eaves et al., 2016; Mey et al., 2016). These studies consisted of running ice flow models forward and fitting observed moraines by optimizing some of the model parameters. A key component in such models is the mass balance, which defines ice accumulation and ablation, and is thus primarily a function of precipitation and temperature (Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). Several models exist to simulate mass balance, from the simple Positive Degree Day model (Braithwaite, 1995) to more sophisticated energy mass balance models (Oerlemans, 1992, 1997; Becker et al., 2016; Pellicciotti et al., 2016). These models have been successfully applied to reconstruct glacial history (Becker et al., 2016; Seguinot et al., 2018), but require knowledge of a large number of uncertain parameters, which might change over a glacial cycle. In depth analysis of ice flow models used for paleoclimatic reconstructions can be found in the paper by Kirchner and others (2016).

In practice, past ice thicknesses are poorly constrained. Recent studies on the European Alps have emphasized the systematic mismatch between paleo ice flow model and reconstruction from trimlines (e.g., Cohen et al., 2017; Seguinot et al., 2018), in terms of ice thickness. Here we introduce an inversion method to infer spatially varying mass balance information from the former extent of glaciers derived from geomorphological observations, such as moraines. We apply a gradient descent method to minimize a cost function, which includes the misfit between modeled and geomorphological maximal glacial extents and a regularization term to ensure sufficient smoothness of the inverted variables. As a result, the method consists of running a forward model a large number of times with a tuning of the mass balance at each iteration. The ice flow model is modeled by solving the mass conservation equation using the

shallow ice approximation (SIA) (Mahaffy, 1976; Hutter, 1983) and the developed codes are accelerated using Graphic Processing Units (GPUs).

Below, we first introduce the basic equations governing our forward model. Then we present the theoretical basis behind the method and provide a step by step recipe for its numerical implementation. We then illustrate the method's efficiency for constraining spatial variations in mass balance over mountain ranges with a series of examples.

2.2 Forward model

2.2.1 Ice dynamics

At the time scale relevant for ice sheet dynamics, ice can be described as a viscous and incompressible non-Newtonian fluid (Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). Ice thickness can be modeled by solving the mass conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + b, \quad (2.1)$$

where H is the ice thickness, \mathbf{q} is the horizontal ice flux and b represents the mass balance rate. Horizontal ice flux is defined as vertically integrated velocity field $\mathbf{q} = \int_B^S \mathbf{u} dz$, and we approximate velocities using the SIA:

$$\mathbf{u}(z) = - \underbrace{A(\rho g)^n [H^{n+1} + (S-z)^{n+1}] |\nabla S|^{n-1} \nabla S}_{(i)} + \underbrace{A_s (\rho g)^n H^{n-1} |\nabla S|^{n-1} \nabla S}_{(ii)}, \quad (2.2)$$

where (i) represents the deformation velocity and (ii) represents the sliding velocity, S is the surface altitude, ρ is density of ice, g is the gravitational acceleration, A is the ice flow parameter, A_s is a sliding parameter and n is the Glen flow law exponent. Values for the flow parameters A and A_s are taken from Oerlemans (1997) (who used values from Budd, 1979), and can be found listed in Table 1, along with the other parameter values used in the model.

The SIA is based on the assumption that large ice bodies are mainly deformed by vertical shear stress, and therefore neglects longitudinal stresses in the mass conservation equation (Eq A1). We are using this approximation with the assumption that the horizontal scale of the ice extent is much larger than the vertical scale ($H \ll L$). Solving of full set of Stokes equations, a full set of momentum equations, would give more realistic results (especially near the margin and ice divide). However, the ice extent is primarily a function of mass balance, topography and ice dynamics. Since we only consider the extent of ice as forward model output in our inversion method, we restrict our analysis to the SIA.

Table 2.1: *Ice flow model parameters*

	Constants	Value	Units
A	Ice-flow parameter	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$\text{Pa}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$
A_s	Sliding flow parameter	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-20}$	$\text{Pa}^{-3}\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$
ρ	Ice density	910	kgm^{-3}
g	Gravitational constant	9.81	ms^{-2}
n	Exponent in Glen flow law	3	

The mass balance rate, b , is defined as the annual gain, accumulation, or loss of mass, ablation, at the glacier surface (e.g., Oerlemans, 2001; Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). We define the mass balance rate, b , as a spatially varying variable:

$$b = \min(\beta(S(x, y) - E(x, y)), c), \quad (2.3)$$

where β is the balance rate gradient, E is the equilibrium line altitude (i.e., the location where accumulation is equal to ablation) and c is a maximum ice accumulation rate (e.g., Meier, 1962; Kessler et al., 2006; Oerlemans, 2008). The evolution of the ice cap or glacier surface is in part determined by the mass balance rate and its values depend on the local climate conditions. Mass balance rate is positive in the accumulation area and negative in the ablation area. The mass balance gradient, β , tends to be steeper in the ablation than accumulation area (Mayo, 1984). To keep the problem simple for introducing the inversion method, we choose the balance gradient to be constant.

Solving Eq. (A1) using the SIA (Mahaffy, 1976; Hutter, 1983) leads to a non-linear diffusion-reaction type equation that can be solved numerically (Hindmarsh and Payne, 1996). In that case, the ice flux \mathbf{q} is defined as

$$\mathbf{q} = -D\nabla S, S = H + B, \quad (2.4)$$

where B is the bedrock and D is the diffusivity expressed as:

$$D = (\rho g)^n [AH^{n+2} + A_s H^n] |\nabla S|^{(n-1)}. \quad (2.5)$$

Table 1.

The main advantage of models based on using SIA to solve the mass conservation equation Eq. (A1) is their computational efficiency, which we further enhance using GPUs. The details of the numerical implementation we use can be found in the Appendix A. Note, however, that the inversion method approach we propose can be used with other types of approximations for ice flow, such as solving a full set of Stokes equations or a higher order approximation

of these equations (e.g., Pattyn 2003; Egholm et al. 2011), as long as it is computationally possible. For the moment, running 1000-3000 inversion model runs with higher order models without the use of GPUs is not practical.

2.3 Inversion method

In this section, we provide the theoretical basis of the inversion method and its numerical implementation.

2.3.1 Theoretical basis

Our objective is to invert a known ice extent into a spatially variable E using the forward model explained in section 2. The forward problem is defined as:

$$h_m(x, y) = F(E(x, y), \beta), \quad (2.6)$$

where $h_m(x, y)$ is the data we are trying to fit (note that $h(x, y)$ is used for ice extent and $H(x, y)$ for ice thickness), F is the forward model (the ice flow model), and $E(x, y)$ and β are the unknown parameters of the mass balance equation, Eq. (A1), we wish to constrain. Below we derive the method to infer $E(x, y)$ and show it can be extended to β .

As with any inversion method, the primary objective is to minimize the misfit between the model predictions and the observations. To do so, we define a misfit function $G(E)$ as a spatially integrated difference between the ice extent calculated for a forward model, $h_m(x, y)$, and the observations, $h_o(x, y)$ as:

$$G(E) = \frac{1}{2} \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))^2 dx dy, \quad (2.7)$$

where $[0, L_x] \times [0, L_y]$ is our computational domain. The chosen computational domain strictly contains the area where thickness is positive, i.e., we have $S = B$ in the neighborhood of the border of the domain. The goal is then to minimize the misfit function G by varying $E(x, y)$ iteratively.

We now look for a descent direction to define a sequence of E_i , which minimizes the misfit function G . For that purpose, we formally compute $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$, the directional derivative of G with respect to E along a given direction δE :

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = - \int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} \delta E dx dy. \quad (2.8)$$

The term $\frac{\partial h_m}{\partial E}$ represents the change of ice extent with respect to E , which are both function of x and y .

The goal of the inversion is to minimize G , and thus make $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$ negative. However, the inverse problem is underdetermined (Hansen, 1994; Zhang and Xu, 2011). We solve this by imposing some form of regularization. Here we assume a smooth solution and impose smoothness on E using a Tikhonov regularization (Tikhonov, 1963; Poplavskii et al., 2001). We do this by defining a new misfit function G , now containing the regularization term:

$$G(E) = \frac{1}{2} \int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[\underbrace{(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))^2}_{(i)} + \tau_2 \underbrace{\left[\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right]}_{(ii)} \right] dx dy, \quad (2.9)$$

(i) in Eq.(2.9) is the same as in Eq.(2.7), while (ii) imposes the smoothness on the solution. The parameter τ_2 is a positive constant which acts as the additional constraint of smoothness. A large constant would force the solution to be very smooth, while a small or zero constant would cancel this constraint. Following the same derivation as above for (ii):

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \delta E + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \delta E \right) dx dy, \quad (2.10)$$

and using the integration by parts:

$$\int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \delta E + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \delta E \right] dx dy = \left[\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \right) \delta E \right]_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} - \int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} \delta E + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \delta E \right) dx dy. \quad (2.11)$$

Because the first term on the right hand side becomes negligible, as there is no ice on the boundaries of the model we can choose E in the a neighborhood of the border such that $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} = 0$, so $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$ becomes:

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \int\int_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[-\tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta E dx dy, \quad (2.12)$$

which combined with Eq. (2.8) gives:

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(-\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} \right) - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta E dx dy. \quad (2.13)$$

Following the same logic, one can perform the same development for β instead of E :

$$\langle G'(\beta), \delta \beta \rangle = \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(-\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial \beta} \right) - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta \beta dx dy. \quad (2.14)$$

2.3.2 Numerical implementation of the inverse algorithm

To this end, we use the gradient descent method (Press 2007, Fletcher 2013), in which $E(x, y)$ is updated with the following increment:

$$\delta E = - \left[\tau_1 (h_o - h_m) - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right]. \quad (2.15)$$

This choice of δE leads to a decrease of the misfit G , assuming an appropriate choice of the iteration parameters τ_1 and τ_2 , which are positive constants. We show below that recombining and substituting Eq. (2.15) into Eq. (2.13) results in negative increment of the misfit G :

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} \left[-\delta E - (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} + \tau_1 \right) \right] \delta E dx dy. \quad (2.16)$$

Sorting Eq. (2.16) leads to:

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = - \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} [\delta E]^2 dx dy - \iint_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} + \tau_1 \right) \delta E dx dy. \quad (2.17)$$

One can see that Eq. (2.17) is negative if the term $(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))$ is sufficiently small, in other words the method converges if our initial guess is not too far from the final solution.

In practice, we follow the steps of the inversion algorithm presented in Table 2. First, we start by assigning an initial guess for E (step I). We arbitrarily choose an equilibrium line altitude field, E , and add some white noise to avoid imposing a spatial pattern to the solution,

Table 2.2: *Implementation of the inversion algorithm described in Equations*

Inversion Algorithm	
I.	Assign initial guesses for E
II.	Run the forward SIA model $F(E, \beta)$, mass balance rate b is calculated using (Eq.(2)).
III.	Output of the forward model, the ice extent (h), is used to calculate an error function γ : $\gamma = h_o - h_m$
IV.	Update the E by multiplying the error function γ with accompanying parameters: $E = E - \tau_1 \gamma$
V.	The problem is regularized by applying diffusion to updated E $E = E + \tau_2 \nabla^2 E$
VI.	Repeat steps II to V until γ is minimized

and therefore avoid the influence of the initial guess on the solution. Adding random noise enables to test whether the method can retrieve a meaningful solution or not, even with a poor initial guess. Next, the mass conservation equation Eq.(A1) is solved using the mass balance rate field, (b), calculated using the input E , Eq.(A1), and the model is run until a steady state is reached, i.e., the ice thickness and ice extent do not change (step II). The output of the forward model, i.e., the ice extent, is used to calculate γ (step III). We define γ as the difference between observed ice extent data and ice extent calculated from a forward model run. Note that although the algorithm works using ice thickness (H), we rarely know it. In that case, we calculate ice extent (h) by setting ice thickness equal to 1 where there is ice, and equal to 0 where there is no ice. Step IV consists of updating the equilibrium line altitude locally by increasing (or decreasing) it where the modeled ice extent/ice thickness was found large (or small). If the glacier is too thick or goes beyond the ice extent, E is raised. Conversely, E is lowered if the glacier extent is too small. We then regularize the problem by applying diffusion on E using τ_2 (step V) for a chosen number of diffusion iterations, n_{sm} . Step IV and V correspond to one step of the descent direction given by Eq.(2.15). Finally, we return to step II, and iterate until γ is minimized (step VI). In the case where we want to invert for β instead of E , the described steps remain the same. One only needs to replace E with β in the equations since the equations are identical.

The parameters τ_1 and τ_2 are positive scalar values, which must be chosen. Both τ_1 and τ_2 are problem dependent. The choice is based mainly on the spatial dimensions of the problem and the spatial variability of the solution.

Furthermore, the choice of the inversion update parameter τ_1 reflects on the precision of the result. Too high a value will make it difficult for the inversion algorithm to converge to the solution because of too large jumps in value of E after each inversion step. On the other hand, a small value, after applying diffusion, might not result in a change in E that is sufficiently large enough to modify the ice extent of an area, thus not enable to fit the data successfully.

Diffusion in step V represents the smoothness one wishes to impose on E . We do this by iteratively solving the diffusion equation using a fully explicit scheme. The degree of smoothness is set by the number of iterations used in the explicit scheme. A large number of diffusion iterations may lead to a very smooth solution, and might not enable to capture local variations in mass balance rate. In contrast, a small number of diffusion iterations leads to overfitting the data. We must keep in mind that we are fitting the ice extent by varying only one physical parameter, E , and that differences between observations and our model output could come also from the assumptions made in our forward model. The choice of number of diffusion iteration is illustrated later on.

We would like to stress here, the algorithm shows that the method only requires computing ice thickness and the Laplacian of E .

2.4 Results

In this section, we illustrate the efficiency of the method with a series of synthetic examples. We start with a simple 2D problem and then present a 2D synthetic example using real topography (Uinta Mountains). In the simple 2D example we show, in separate experiments, that the method can invert the ice extent in order to recover both E and β , while in the Uinta Mountains example we show that one can use ice thickness as well as ice extent to reconstruct E . Finally, we show how the method can be applied to a natural example at the LGM in the South Island of New Zealand. In the following experiments ice extents are presumed to be reached at the same time, steady state solution, and sliding is parametrized to be constant. The balance gradient, β , is also kept constant in all examples except where we use the method to recover β . Since we can only do our inversion in the area of the map where we have ice, the results will also be presented only within the ice extent.

2.4.1 2-dimensional inversion

For this 2D case, we present two experiments. First, we invert the synthetic ice extent and assess whether the method enables us to recover the prescribed E , and in the second experiment we show that the method is capable to recover β as well. The ice thickness, hence ice extent as well, are simulated by prescribing an arbitrary E and β .

A combination of two simple Gaussian shapes is used for the bedrock:

$$B = B_0 \left[\exp \left(-\frac{X^2}{10^{10}} - \frac{Y^2}{10^9} \right) + \exp \left(-\frac{X^2}{10^9} - \frac{(Y - \frac{L_y}{8})^2}{10^{10}} \right) \right], \quad (2.18)$$

Table 2.3: 2D inversion parameters

	Constants	Value	Units
B_0	Max. bedrock elevation	3500	m
β	Mass balance gradient	0.01	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	100	
n_y	Number of points in y	100	
L_x	Length scale in x	250000	m
L_y	Length scale in y	200000	m
n_{sm}	Number of diffusion iterations (both cases)	30	
$\tau_1(E)$	E inversion update parameter	390	m
$\tau_1(\beta)$	β inversion update parameter	0.015	a^{-1}
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter (both cases)	$0.25 \cdot \min(\text{dx}^2, \text{dy}^2)$	m^2

where B_0 is the maximum bedrock elevation, X and Y represent the matrices of distance vectors, and L_y is the length scale in the y-direction. The prescribed E_o we wish to recover is defined as follows:

$$E_o = 2150 + 900 \arctan\left(\frac{Y}{L_y}\right). \quad (2.19)$$

In this experiment β is constant and set to 0.01. The initial guess is equal to 3000 m with 400 m amplitude white noise.

In the second experiment, we show that the method enables to recover the mass balance gradient, β . For this we use the same setup as above, i.e., bedrock is defined as in Eq. (2.18), and E as in Eq. (2.19). We prescribe β_o we wish to recover:

$$\beta_o = 0.01 + 0.015 \arctan\left(\frac{X}{L_x}\right), \quad (2.20)$$

where L_x is the length scale in the x-direction.

Fig. 2.1 shows the calculated E and β (Fig. 2.1A and Fig. 2.1C) and the differences between our inversions and the prescribed values (Fig. 2.1B and Fig. 2.1D). In both cases, during the inversion, convergence is reached when the differences between the forward model output ice extent differs from our synthetic "observations" by less than 10 points. The results show that convergence is reached after 293 iterations for E and 149 iterations for β . More importantly, the two results demonstrate that it is possible to recover E and β using this approach, and capture the spatial variation that was imposed by Eq. (2.19) and Eq. (2.20) and illustrated in Fig. 2.1A and Fig. 2.1C. The parameters used in this test are summarized in Table 3.

Figure 2.1: (A) shows the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (B) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the ice extent), (C) shows the calculated (modeled) β using our inversion algorithm, (D) difference between synthetic and calculated β where there is ice (within the ice extent).

2.4.2 2-dimensional inversion, Uinta Mountains synthetic test

Now the method is applied to a real topography. In this example, we show that the method is capable of restoring spatially variable E by using the ice extent as well as ice thickness as data. The Uinta Mountains, North America, was used as bedrock topography (Fig. 2.2A). The topography was extracted from the SRTM data (Jarvis and others, 2008) and smoothed using a median filter.

First, a forward model was run with a prescribed E_o , which includes some spatial variability. The imposed pattern follows a N-S arc tangent form. The ice extent is derived from the calculated ice thickness, which then represents the synthetic observations that we wish to invert for mass balance. The ice extent is calculated by setting the ice thickness equal to 1 where there is ice, and to 0 where there is not. Furthermore, high peaks that pierce through the ice are not included in our misfit calculations. The initial guess for E_m field is 3100 m with 400 m amplitude random white noise added to it. To assess the performance of the inversion scheme, the sum of differences between the synthetic E_o field and the calculated E_m are monitored. All parameters used can be found in Table 4.

The results of the inversion for the E_m field are represented and compared with the prescribed E_o field in Fig. 2.2B. The differences between the prescribed solution E_o and inversion model

Table 2.4: *Uinta Mountains inversion experiment parameters*

	Constants	Value	Units
β	Mass balance gradient	0.007	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	512	
n_y	Number of points in y	512	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	339.56	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	242.44	m
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	150000	
n_{iter}	Number invers iterations	1000	
τ_1	E inversion update parameter	150	m
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter	14336	m^2
n_{sm_1}	Number of diffusion iterations - Fig. 4B	50	
n_{sm_2}	Number of diffusion iterations - Fig. 5A	5	
n_{sm_3}	Number of diffusion iterations - Fig. 5B	5000	

solution E_m are less than 30 m, which falls under 5% difference from the prescribed solution (Fig. 2.2C).

We now repeat the same test with the same forcing, but instead of using the ice extent we randomly chose ice thickness points on our synthetic glacier. Out of 40317 ice thickness points within the ice extent we chose 433 (Fig. 2.9A). The only difference in the approach from the previous example is that now we calculate γ as a difference of ice thickness values in the chosen points between calculated and synthetic ice. The resulting figures (Fig. 2.9 in Appendix B) and tables with used parameters can be found in Appendix B.

Now we investigate the influence of the number of the diffusion iterations. We report two different end-member cases. The first one uses only 5 diffusion iterations (Fig. 2.3A) and the second uses 5000 iterations (Fig. 2.3B). Fig. 2.3 shows the differences between the E_o for the two end-member tests. It appears that the choice of the number of diffusion iterations strongly influences the precision of the result. A large number of diffusion iterations reduces the spatial variability in mass balance, and is thus filtering out any local gradient, whereas a small number of diffusion iterations reduces the rate at which the residuals are decreased (Fig. 2.4).

2.4.3 Inversion of LGM ice extent in the South Island of New Zealand

To verify the method for a real situation, we reconstruct the LGM mass balance using the observed ice extent of the South Island of New Zealand (Barrell, 2011). This example offers us the possibility of comparing the results with previous reconstructions (Golledge et al., 2012).

The South Island's climate is heavily influenced by the Westerlies. As the air flows across the Southern Alps, precipitation is orographically enhanced with up to 10 m/yr of precipitation

Figure 2.2: (A) shows the bedrock map used (Uinta Mountains) with the synthetic ice extent, (B) is the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (C) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines extent).

Figure 2.3: (A) is the difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines ice extent) with number of diffusion iterations set to 5, (B) is the difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice with number diffusion of iterations set to 5000.

Figure 2.4: Residuals calculated as a sum of differences between the synthetic E and the calculated E where there is ice. The red dots represent residuals for the case shown in Figure 2.3A, green for case shown in Figure 2.3B and blue the case from Figure 2.2

Table 2.5: *New Zealand inversion experiment parameters*

	Constants	Value	Units
β	Mass balance gradient	0.02	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	1024	
n_y	Number of points in y	1024	
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	110000	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	668.99	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	646.51	m
n_{iter}	Number invers iterations	3000	
τ_{1_1}	E inversion update parameter - test A	100	m
τ_{2_1}	Diffusion update parameter - test A	101944	m^2
n_{sm_1}	Number of diffusion iterations - test A	100	
τ_{1_2}	E inversion update parameter - test B	25	m
τ_{2_2}	Diffusion update parameter - test B	20389	m^2
n_{sm_2}	Number of diffusion iterations - test B	5	

on the west side (Henderson and Thompson, 1999). The eastern slopes see considerably lower rates of precipitation (about 1 m/yr) as a consequence of the westerly airflow across the mountain range.

In the past, the Southern Alps have experienced extensive glaciations, including full transitions from glacial to fluvial processes (Whitehouse, 1988). Climate has controlled the growth and decay of mountain glaciers in New Zealand since at least 2.4-2.6 Ma (Suggate, 1990), as testified by an exceptional moraine record across the entire South Island (Barrell, 2011). During the LGM, the North Atlantic meridional overturning circulation was weakened compared to present, the Intertropical Convergence Zone shifted southward, which in the southern mid-latitudes modified the location of wind and temperature (Rojas et al., 2009; Denton et al., 2010; McGlone et al., 2010). The LGM was thus marked by changes in regional atmospheric conditions that affected winds and precipitation in the Southern Alps, which may have led to a change in humidity, possibly up to 25% drier than today (Golledge et al., 2012). Temperatures were between 4° and 8°C lower than today (Newnham et al., 1989; Barrows et al., 2007; Golledge et al., 2012; Seltzer et al., 2015). Most importantly, despite these changes, the orographically enhanced precipitation was preserved during the LGM. This contrast of precipitation is also observed in the position of the equilibrium line altitude, E , on either side of the mountain range (Golledge et al., 2012). Therefore, the spatial variation in E provides us with an appropriate test.

In this inversion, we constrain $E(x, y)$ using the LGM ice extent (Barrell, 2011) shown in Fig. 2.5A. For simplicity, we use the present day bedrock with all elevations below sea level set to zero. Note, we assume that the ice extent obtained from data is reached at the same time over its entire length. All parameter values used for this test can be found in Table 5.

Figure 2.5: Application of the inverse algorithm to the South Island of New Zealand. (A) Bedrock map used (gray) with the LGM ice extent obtained from Barrell (2011) (green), (B) calculated (modeled) E field using our inverse algorithm where there is ice (Test A), (C) E field calculated with the second set of parameters using our inverse algorithm where there is ice (Test B).

We present two model results, test A and test B, for two different sets of τ_1 , τ_2 and n_{sm} . Both test results (Fig. 2.5) exhibit a clear north - south gradient in the elevation of E , as well as the west - east gradient. The N-S change could be the result of the temperature change because of the latitudinal differences, making the southern areas colder and with larger accumulation zones, and in turn lower E values. The W-E gradient reflects the influence of the westerly winds bringing precipitation to the west side, thus increasing the accumulation and lowering the altitude of E , while the east side is drier with less accumulation and higher E .

In the second test, test B, we reduce the values of the update parameters, τ_1 and τ_2 , and the number of diffusion steps n_{sm} . Reducing n_{sm} leads to more local variations. Smaller τ_2 (five times smaller than the first test) reduces the influence of smoothing, while a smaller τ_1 results in smaller changes in E between iterations, all resulting in a more precise fit. Fig. 2.6A and Fig. 2.6B show the differences between the observed (data) and calculated ice extent (model) for each test. Test B enables to better fit the data, although it does it at the expense of creating local depressions in E . This information is lost in the first test because higher smoothing, n_{sm} , acts as a filter of local variations. It is worth keeping in mind that we are showing the results of the inversion algorithm varying only one parameter, E . This results in overfitting the data and neglecting the influence of other physical processes ignored in the model as well as approximations made in the forward model, as stated above.

2.5 Discussion and Conclusions

The main goal of this paper is to present a simple inversion method to reconstruct the spatially variable mass balance and equilibrium line altitude (E) fields using ice extent data. This approach offers the possibility of constraining past climates in glaciated mountain ranges.

Figure 2.6: Differences between the observed and modeled ice extents. (A) Test A. (B) Test B. Yellow represents areas where the data has ice but the model output does not, the red is where the model output calculates ice and the data shows there was no ice in those areas.

The inverse method is based on a Tikhonov regularization and computationally, besides the forward model, only requires the calculation of a diffusion equation. In order to show the range of applications of the method we have constructed 6 experiments, both synthetic and natural, whose results are presented. To significantly reduce the calculation time necessary for our inverse model we have implemented the codes to run on GPUs.

In the first experiment, the 2D synthetic case, we have shown the method is capable of reconstructing a spatially variable E as well as a spatially variable β on a simple topography, consisting of a combination of two Gaussian bumps, using ice extent (Fig. 2.1). The second experiment is the 2D synthetic case using real topography (Uinta Mountains) where we show that the method can successfully reconstruct spatially variable E , defined as an arctangent function from N-S, using only ice extent as constraint for our inversion. We first ran our forward ice flow model with a chosen setup and then used the calculated ice extent as synthetic observations to invert E we originally used. The error while recovering E is less than 5% (Fig. 2.2C). The same was done in the experiment using ice thickness points presented in Appendix B. The difference is that instead of the ice extent we are using randomly chosen ice thickness points (Fig. 2.9A). Fig. 2.9 in Appendix B shows that the method can do the inversion successfully. When analyzing errors of the results obtained using ice extent (Fig. 2.2C) and ice thickness (Fig. 2.9C) we can see that using the ice extent the largest error is in the middle of the ice extent and the opposite effect using ice thickness. This happens

because the method is more precise in places where it is better constrained by data. In the ice extent case, the errors are smaller on the edges, and in the ice thickness case errors are larger on the edges and smaller inside the ice because of the distribution of our ice thickness points.

The influence of different number of diffusion iteration has been presented (Fig. 2.3A, Fig. 2.3B). It is clear that too many diffusion iterations will result in losing the spatial variability of the result, while too little iterations will not propagate the update from the edges of the ice efficiently to its middle.

In order to verify the method we applied it to a real case, the LGM ice extent of the South Island of New Zealand (Barrell, 2011). The assumption made in this experiment is that the entire ice extent is reached at the same time, representing something close to the LGM steady state. Our inversion result for the first test is similar in both pattern and values to the reconstruction done by other authors (Golledge et al., 2012). Fig. 2.5B shows a clear N-S gradient, which corresponds to the latitudinal change and is thus controlled by temperature, and a clear W-E gradient, which corresponds to the influence of the Westerlies and is thus controlled by precipitation. The second result is an example of overfitting the data. It is important to emphasize that the model setup for this experiment is simplified, which is one of the reasons for the mismatches between the observed and calculated ice extent (Fig. 2.6B). The bedrock topography used was the current one and the values below sea level were set to 0, thus ignoring calving. Basal sliding was parameterized as a constant value, while basal melting was not taken into account. The influence of isostasy was ignored, which is not a valid assumption for such an ice mass, and is most likely the reason E elevations are higher than expected. Despite these limitations our method is still able to invert the spatial pattern, both the N-S and W-E gradients, and recover values close to other reconstructions.

The experiments presented show several possible applications. In order to obtain a more accurate reconstruction of mass balance parameters for large mountain ranges, the forward model needs to be improved to include the effects of isostasy. The choice of bedrock topography for a certain time period remains a setback. The use of present day topography for LGM neglects the change in the amount, distribution and thickness of eroded and deposited sediments since the LGM. Sediment filled valleys today might have been empty or not even eroded. This influences where our ice can flow in forward model calculations, changing the resulting ice extent and therefore our inverse calculations.

The role of β has not been fully addressed in cases where we attempt to recover E . In the presented experiments the balance gradient β was set to be constant value, and chosen arbitrarily. Future work will include an expansion of the method in order to recover both spatially variable E and β fields. Computationally, adding the inversion of another parameter in the algorithm would only require the calculation of an additional diffusion equation for β .

Similar methods to quantify climate parameters (temperature, precipitation, mass balance, equilibrium line altitude) using ice extents have been developed by other authors (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Kessler et al. 2006; Golledge et al. 2012; Rowan et al. 2014). The approaches differ in defining the climate forcing (energy balance model, positive degree day model, net mass balance Eq. (A1)), and the ice flow models used vary in complexity. Some authors use current day conditions or present-day mean annual temperature and precipitation measurements to produce scenarios where these parameters are uniformly changed, temperature reduction by -1°C or precipitation lowered by 25%, and then compare ice flow model calculations with observations. The main difference with our approach is that our inversion algorithm works as a spatially variable optimization.

Overall, we show that by calculating only an additional diffusion equation, the method is capable to reproduce the general pattern of a spatially variable E over a mountain range using ice extent data.

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2.7 Appendix

2.8 Appendix A - Numerical implementation of the forward model

Eq. (A1) is solved explicitly using the finite difference method (FDM) on a staggered grid (Hindmarsh and Payne, 1996). Fig. 2.7 is a schematic presentation of a staggered grid. The ice thickness points are in the nodes of the grid, while fluxes are in between the nodes and

the diffusivities are in the middle of the cell. To conserve mass and avoid unrealistically large fluxes that can occur when using the SIA on high resolutions and steep terrains (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Jarosch et al., 2013), we have implemented a flux correction for diffusivity calculations based on an algorithm inspired by Wang et al. (2011). This changes how B , H and the slope ∇S in Eq. (2.4) and Eq. (2.5) are calculated compared to Hindmarsh and Payne (1996) and substantially helps the convergence of our forward model. The topography and ice thickness are computed as follows:

$$\tilde{B}_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} = \max[B_{i,j}, B_{i+1,j}, B_{i,j+1}, B_{i+1,j+1}], \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\tilde{H}_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{4} \max[0, S_{i,j} - \tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j} - \tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1} - \tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1} - \tilde{B}], \quad (\text{A2})$$

and the slope:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial x} \approx \frac{\max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j}) + \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1})}{2dx}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial y} \approx \frac{\max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j}) + \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j})}{2dy}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

and the squared norm:

$$|\nabla S|^2 = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial y}\right)^2. \quad (\text{A5})$$

Finally, the fluxes in x and y direction are defined as:

$$q_{x(i+\frac{1}{2},j)} = \frac{D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} + D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \frac{\max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i,j+1}), S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i,j+1}), S_{i,j+1})}{dx}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$q_{y(i,j+\frac{1}{2})} = \frac{D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} + D_{i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \frac{\max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i+1,j}), S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i+1,j}), S_{i+1,j})}{dy}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Combining the above expressions gives us the divergence of the flux:

$$\nabla \cdot q \approx \frac{q_{x(i+\frac{1}{2},j)} - q_{x(i-\frac{1}{2},j)}}{dx} + \frac{q_{y(i,j+\frac{1}{2})} - q_{y(i,j-\frac{1}{2})}}{dy}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

Figure 2.7: Scheme of the staggered grid

Because we are solving our equations explicitly, our time step dt is strongly restricted by the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition, resulting in many forward model iterations before converging to a solution. We balance this by writing our codes for GPUs, which significantly increase our computational efficiency. GPUs are specialized for intensive highly parallel computation (graphics rendering) with more transistors devoted to data processing rather than data caching and flow control (NVIDIA, 2017). Since we are only interested in steady state solutions of Eq. (A1), we accelerate the convergence using a local time-step, such that

$$dt_{i,j}^t = \min\left(\frac{1}{c}, c_{stab} \frac{\min(dx^2, dy^2)}{\epsilon + \tilde{D}_{i,j}^t}\right), \quad (\text{A9})$$

where dx and dy is the spatial step, $dt_{i,j}^t$ is the local time at each iteration, c is the maximum ice accumulation rate from Eq. (A1), c_{stab} is the time step coefficient (Courant number, for 2D cases in this paper set to 1/8.1), ϵ is a small number (10^{-3}) and $\tilde{D}_{i,j}^t$ is the spatially averaged value of diffusivity for a given point (i, j) for the current (t) iteration. Note here that one can solve the steady-state state solution of the reaction-diffusion equation directly as a non-linear elliptic equation (Jouvet et al., 2008, 2011; Jouvet and Bueler, 2012).

Because solving our inverse problem explicitly may require a large number of iterations, thousands of inverse model iterations and tens to hundreds of thousands forward model iterations, or if we are interested in either high resolution or continental scale problems, we accelerate the code on GPUs using the parallel computing platform CUDA created by NVIDIA (Mikovic, 2009; NVIDIA, 2017). Other authors have also implemented ice flow models for GPUs (Brdstrup et al., 2014).

When implemented on GPU, the computation time for our forward model to calculate 110k iterations, and reach steady state, on a 1024x1024 grid takes around 113 s using GeForce GTX TITAN black card, and 76 s using TITAN X card, both cards were used to for our experiments and both are gaming cards, while one iteration step takes around 121 s and under 80 s, respectively. This number varies with the model of the GPU used. Just as an example to solve the same forward problem with the same setup on a professional GPU NVIDIA Tesla V100 takes 24 s. The forward model was benchmarked using the experiment proposed by Jarosch et al. (2013) (Fig. 2.8).

2.9 Appendix B - Uinta example using ice thickness

Here we present the result and the values used for the inversion experiment using ice thickness values instead of ice extent. Fig. 2.9A represents the result of the method while Fig. 2.9B

Figure 2.8: Comparison between our numerical solution and the benchmark provided from Jarosch and others (2013). The red line represents the bedrock topography; the blue line is the analytical solution. The blue dots are the numerical solution of our forward model.

shows the differences between the calculated E and a synthetic one. Parameter values used in the setup can be found in Table 6.

Table 2.6: *Uinta Mountains ice thickness experiment*

	Constants	Value	Units
β	Mass balance gradient	0.007	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	512	
n_y	Number of points in y	512	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	339.56	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	242.44	m
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	150000	
n_{iter}	Number invers iterations	1000	
τ_1	E inversion update parameter	14	m
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter	11712	m^2
n_{sm}	Number of diffusion iterations	130	

Figure 2.9: Results of the inversion algorithm using ice thickness points instead of ice extent (A) position of the randomly chosen ice thickness points with color corresponding to their altitude (point size not to scale), (B) is the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (C) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines extent).

CHAPTER 3

Climatic patterns over the European Alps during the LGM derived from
inversion of the paleo-ice extent

Vjeran Višnjević¹, Frédéric Herman¹, Günther Prasicek²

¹Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne

²Interdisciplinary Center for Mountain Research, University of Lausanne

Abstract

Quaternary climate has been dominated by alternating glacial and interglacial periods. While the timing and extent of past ice caps are well documented, local variations in temperature and precipitation as a response to cyclic glaciations are not resolved. Resolving these issues is necessary for understanding regional and global climate circulation. In particular, the impact of the cold high-pressure zone above the Fennoscandian ice cap on the position of the jet stream in Europe, and a possible change in the direction and the source of moisture flow are still discussed. Here we reconstruct climate conditions that led to the observed ice extent in the European Alps during the last glacial maximum (LGM). Using a new inverse method to reconstruct the spatially variable position of the equilibrium line altitude (ELA), we investigate whether southern shifts in the position of the Westerlies may have influenced the growth and retreat of the ice cap. We report inversion results that enable us to estimate the role of climate, inversion method parameters, ice dynamics, flexure and topography in modulating the inferred equilibrium line altitude. Our main finding is the presence of a dominating W-E gradient in the position of the ELA during the LGM that does not require a shift of the westerlies during the LGM.

3.1 Introduction

The last glacial maximum (LGM), spanning from 26.5 ka to 20 ka (Clark et al., 2009), represents the last large dominating cold period with its legacy still imprinted on the present-day topography (e.g., Clark et al., 2009). The advent of numerical models (climate (Strandberg et al., 2011), ocean (Mikolajewicz 2011), glacial (Seguinot et al., 2018), vegetation (Janská et al., 2017)), the development of new methods and an increase in available proxy data (pollen, SST, speleothems) open opportunities to improve our understanding of the climate conditions during the LGM and the interplay between glacial and climate processes that led to these conditions.

A significant body of work on LGM climate conditions in Europe provides estimates on precipitation and temperature patterns. Yet, uncertainties remain, highlighted by the discrepancies that exist between proxy data and models (Jost et al., 2005; Ramstein et al., 2007). Pollen-based reconstructions (Peyron et al., 1998) suggest a mean annual temperature depression, compared to today, of $12 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$, a mean coldest month depression of $30 \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$, and a decrease in mean annual precipitation of 800 ± 100 mm ($60 \pm 20\%$ lower than today). In contrast, modeling studies suggest warmer conditions compared to the observations inferred from pollen (Jost et al., 2005; Kageyama et al., 2006; Ramstein et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2007; Strandberg et al., 2011), especially in winter where the discrepancy is up to 10°C for western Europe (Ramstein et al., 2007). However, both pollen analysis (Peyron et al., 1998) and glacier modeling (Heyman et al., 2013; Seguinot et al., 2018) indicate a 33% decrease in precipitation and a west-east temperature gradient during the LGM.

Another unresolved question is the position and intensity of storm tracks during the LGM over Europe (Florineth and Schlüchter 2000; Kageyama et al., 2006; Kuhlemann et al., 2008; Hofer et al., 2012; Luetscher et al., 2015). Three end-member scenarios have been proposed. First, the LGM was dominated by westerly winds like today, but drier (Peyron et al., 1998; Kageyama et al., 2006). Second, there was an overall southward deflection of the jet stream (Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000). Such a shift may be explained by the breaking of the Rossby waves west of the Alps and the influence of the Fennoscandian ice sheet (Florineth and Schlüchter 2000; Luetscher et al., 2015) and would have resulted in the meridional flow of moisture over the Alps from the Mediterranean (Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000; Kuhlemann et al., 2008; Hofer et al., 2012; Luetscher et al., 2015; Monegato et al., 2017). Third, Kuhlemann et al. (2008) proposed that the precipitation pattern was dominated by increased cyclogenesis, both in frequency and intensity, in the western Mediterranean. However, the influence of seasonality and the potential alternation between the zonal (during warm seasons) and meridional (during cold seasons) circulation remains unresolved (Kuhlemann et al., 2008). In any case, the characteristics of the Alpine climate during the LGM should be

reflected in the position of the equilibrium line altitude (ELA) across the Alps and thus in LGM ice thickness and extent.

Ice extent and ice thickness over the Alps during the LGM are constrained by field observations from trimlines, moraines and erratic boulders, as well as from dating of glacial deposits (Bini et al., 2009; Ehlers et al., 2011). Such data serve as both input and validation basis for glacial modeling of the region (Jouvet et al., 2008; Becker et al., 2016; Cohen et al., 2017; Seguinot et al., 2018). Recently, several in-depth modeling studies have been conducted in the Alps, focusing on the LGM. Becker et al. (2016) and Seguinot et al. (2018) used a positive day-degree (PDD) model to parametrize the mass balance, and PISM, a hybrid model combining the shallow ice approximation (SIA; Hutter, 1983) with the shallow shelf approximation (SSA; Morland, 1987), to model ice flow. Cohen et al. (2017) focused their analysis on the Rhine glacier, modeled the full set of momentum equations for viscous fluids using Elmer/Ice (Gagliardini et al., 2013) and parametrized the mass balance as a linear function of surface elevation relative to the equilibrium line altitude. Although modelling studies used a variety of models and parametrizations, they all report a mismatch ranging from 500 m to over 800 m between the modeled ice thickness and geomorphological reconstructions. The reason could be difficulties in assessing the elevation of the ice surface increasing with distance from the mapped trimlines, therefore underestimating the ice thickness in the geomorphological reconstructions. Concerning the modeling, the use of present-day bedrock with or without removal of ice cover and post-glacial sediments, the difficulty to correctly simulate climate patterns in mass balance, the parametrization of ice flow, and spatial variations in timing of the LGM could in part explain the observed mismatch.

In this paper, our objective is to reconstruct the position and spatial variation of the ELA across the Alps during the LGM using a new inverse method (Višnjević et al., 2018) and the mapped ice extent during the LGM (Ehlers et al., 2011). The idea of using ELAs to gain insight into past climate patterns is not new (Callendar et al., 1950). The ELA depends primarily on two climatic variables, precipitation and temperature, which represent the effects of accumulation and ablation, respectively, and, to a lesser extent, radiation (e.g., Ohmura et al., 1992; Oerlemans, 1992). The method introduced by Višnjević et al. (2018) enables us to invert ice extent data for the reconstruction of spatial ELA variations at the scale of a mountain range like the Alps. The model assumes the ice cap to be in a steady state, with the ice sheet in near-equilibrium with climate, a scenario that has been proposed for the LGM (Clark et al., 2009; Monegato et al., 2017). We input the mapped ice extent data as the only climatic constraint because of the above mentioned uncertainties in reconstructed ice thickness. In order to reduce the calculation time, all of the codes are accelerated using graphic card units (GPUs).

Below, we start by explaining the forward ice flow model and the inversion of ice extent for the ELA reconstruction. We then review the topographic data and ice extent used.

We perform a series of inverse model runs with different parameter settings to investigate the sensitivity of the results to the mass balance parameters (mass balance gradient and maximum accumulation rate), the inverse model parameters (initial guess, smoothing, update parameters), ice dynamics (deformation, sliding parameter and constriction factor), flexure (elastic thickness) and bedrock topography. We continue with reporting and interpreting the results and eventually exploit the reconstructed ELA pattern to further constrain the Alpine climate during the LGM.

3.2 Methods

In this section, we summarize the implementation of the forward and the inverse models. Further details can be found in [Višnjević et al. \(2018\)](#). For this study, we added flexural isostasy, a constriction factor for ice flow ([Braun et al. 1999](#)), spatially variable sliding and a damping factor to the forward model.

3.2.1 Forward model implementation

The ice flow model used, presented in [Višnjević et al. \(2018\)](#), is based on the shallow ice approximation (SIA) ([Hutter 1983](#)) and solves the mass conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + b, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where H is the ice thickness and \mathbf{q} is the horizontal ice flux defined as the vertically integrated velocity field. Velocities are approximated using SIA. The mass balance rate, b , is defined as:

$$b = \min(\beta(S(x, y) - ELA(x, y)), c), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where S is the ice surface, β is the mass balance gradient and c is the maximum accumulation rate. Compared to the version of the code presented in [Višnjević et al. \(2018\)](#), we have added flexural isostasy ([Watts, 2001](#)), assuming constant elastic properties and crustal thickness. We further implemented a constriction factor which scales ice velocity depending on cross-sectional curvature of the glacier bed to account for the effect of lateral drag not included in SIA ([Braun et al. 1999](#); [Herman and Braun 2008](#); [Egholm et al. 2011](#)). Sliding is kept constant everywhere except in the accumulation zone where we calculate a 1D analytical solution for basal temperature, T_b , ([Robin, 1955](#); [Braun et al. 1999](#); [Herman and Braun 2008](#); [Cohen et al. 2017](#)) to mimic frozen bed conditions by reducing sliding in areas where T_b is below zero. Basal temperature, T_b , is calculated as:

$$T_b = T_s + \left(\frac{q}{k}\right) \sqrt{\frac{\pi H \kappa}{2b}} \operatorname{erf} \left[\sqrt{\frac{Hb}{2\kappa}} \right], \quad (\text{A3})$$

where κ is the thermal diffusivity of ice, k is the thermal conductivity of the underlying bedrock, q is the surface heat flow and H is the ice thickness. The surface temperature T_s is defined as:

$$T_s = \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial z} \right)_S (S(x, y) - ELA(x, y)), \quad (\text{A4})$$

with the surface temperature gradient $(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial z})_S$ set to constant. Where T_b is smaller than zero, the sliding parameter is adjusted. To avoid large variations at the transition between sliding and frozen-bed, we define the sliding parameter, A_s , as follows:

$$A_s = \begin{cases} f_s \cdot \max(1 + \frac{2}{3} \arctan(T_b), 0.001); & \text{for } M < 0 \text{ and } T_b < 0 \\ f_s & \end{cases}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

The range of A_s goes from f_s for positive T_b , down to the minimum of 0.1% of f_s , where f_s equals $5.7 \cdot 10^{-20} \text{ Pa}^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Budd and others, 1979). A_s is updated every 100 forward model iteration steps to maintain computational performance.

Flexural isostasy is implemented using a Fourier transform solution following (Watts, 2001). To speed-up the calculation, flexure is calculated in the forward model every 1000 iterations, which corresponds to centennial or decennial updates in real time, depending on the time step. Each iteration consists of calculating diffusivity and updating ice thickness H using the mass conservation equation. The updated ice thickness represents the load in the flexure calculation. In order to calculate the full response to the load, we set the size of the Fourier domain 10 times larger than the domain of interest. In the case of the Alps, where the ice flow model calculations are computed on a 1024x1024 grid, we copy that domain to the center of a 10240x10240 grid, for which we calculate the deflection (Watts 2001). We update the bedrock topography B with deflection and recompute all variables which depend on bedrock values, such as diffusivity, constriction factor and flux calculations. The changed bedrock topography is used to update surface altitude S and corresponding mass balance rate b (Eq. (A1)).

Finally, to reduce the number of iterations needed to reach steady state, we also introduce a damping factor into the mass conservation equation following the second-order Richardson iteration method (Frankel, 1950). While iteratively updating the ice thickness, we add an additional percentage of the update from the previous iteration step, resulting in a significantly faster convergence rate.

Table 3.1: *Forward model parameter values kept constant in all scenarios*

	Constants	Value	Units
N	Max. number of inverse iterations	1000	
n_x	Number of points in x	1024	
n_y	Number of points in y	1024	
dx	Spatial resolution in x	784.5	m
dy	Spatial resolution in y	568.4	m
ρ	Ice density	910	kgm ⁻³
g	Gravitational constant	9.81	ms ⁻²
n	Exponent in Glen flow law	568.4	m
A	Deformation parameter	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-24}$	Pa ⁻³ s ⁻¹
f_s	Sliding parameter	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-20}$	Pa ⁻³ m ² s ⁻¹
yr	Seconds per year	31556926	s
c_{stab}	Time step coefficient	0.1235	
q	surface heat flow	$70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	mWm ⁻²
k	Thermal conductivity of underlying bedrock	2.35	Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
$(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z})_S$	Surface temperature gradient	0.005	°Cm ⁻¹
κ	Thermal diffusivity of ice	2.35	m ² s ⁻¹
ρ_a	Asthenosphere density	3300	kgm ⁻³
ν	Poissons ratio	0.25	
Y_m	Youngs module	568.4	Pa

3.2.2 Inversion

A detailed description of the inverse model algorithm can be found in [Višnjević et al. \(2018\)](#). Its objective is to invert ice extent data into a spatially varying and smooth *ELA*. We run the ice flow model until steady state. After each run, we compare the calculated ice extent with the one from observations ([Ehlers et al. 2011](#)) and use this comparison to update the *ELA* ([Višnjević et al. 2018](#)). Note that for each inversion iteration, the convergence of the forward model is the most expensive part. To reduce the convergence time needed for the forward model to reach steady state, we use the calculated ice thickness (H) of the previous inversion iteration step as a starting point for our forward model. This significantly improves the convergence of the forward model for sufficiently small changes in *ELA* between two iterations. The inversion algorithm starts from an initial guess for *ELA* (E_0) and relies mainly on the number of diffusion iterations (n_{sm}) and two parameters (τ_1 and τ_2) that together define the amplitude and amount of smoothing of the final solution. These parameters will be varied in the following sections.

3.3 Data

Bedrock topography, ice extent and mass balance rate parameters (maximum accumulation rate c and mass balance gradient β , (Eq. A1)), are needed as input for our calculations. We use SRTM data (Jarvis and others, 2008) as bedrock topography, where present day ice cover and post-glacial sediments are included. To test how changes in bedrock topography influence the result (Fig. 3.8), we run our model on the bedrock topography provided by Mey et al. (2016), from which the sediment fill has been removed based on a neural network approach. The LGM ice extent used is a simplified version of the ice extent from Ehlers et al. (2011) (Fig. 3.1). The mapped ice extent was simplified because of difficulties with fitting the modeled ice extent to the original south-western border, where only valley glaciers have been mapped and the highest parts of the landscape appear ice free. To test the influence of the mass balance rate parameters on the inversion result we choose a range of values for the maximum accumulation rate c (Table 4.2) representing drier conditions over the Alps reported from both data (pollen) and numerical studies (Peyron et al., 1998; Cohen et al., 2017). The range of values tested for c matches the one from Cohen et al. (2017), where c in their driest and wettest scenarios equals 0.26 m/yr and 1.80 m/yr, respectively. Mass balance gradient β was tested for a larger range of values than reported in other studies (Huss et al., 2008; Cohen et al., 2017), in order to explore potentially different climatic scenarios. Following Huss et al. (2008), typical β for alpine glaciers in the accumulation zone would be $0.009 a^{-1}$, and $0.005 a^{-1}$ in the ablation zone. Although different values for β have been observed in the accumulation and the ablation zone (Mayo, 1984; Huss et al., 2008), and used in modeling studies (Cohen et al., 2017), we keep it constant throughout the ice cap for simplicity in this study.

Glaciation of the Alps during the LGM will also have an impact on topography due to an isostatic effect. The additional load of the large and heavy ice mass bends the lithospheric plate, lowering topography. Removal of that ice during deglaciation results in slow but measurable uplift of the topography. It has recently been argued that most of the currently observed uplift is inherited from the rapid melting of the LGM ice cap (Mey et al., 2016), although this is still a subject of discussion (Sternai et al., 2019). Others argue that up to 60% of this uplift is due to erosion (Champagnac et al., 2007). For our purpose, we must calculate the deflection of the lithosphere and therefore know the elastic thickness of the lithosphere. Unfortunately, estimates vary from 7 to 70 km (Champagnac et al., 2007; Sternai et al., 2013; Mey et al., 2016). In any case, the maximum deflection ranges from 100 m to 280 m, depending on the value for the elastic thickness used (Mey et al., 2016), which is only a fraction of the relief of the Alps.

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of the debated climatic regimes dominating Alpine climate during the LGM: zonal atmospheric circulation (blue) (Peyron et al., 1998), meridional (southern) circulation (red) (Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000), more frequent cyclone generation in the Gulf of Genoa (yellow) (Kuhleemann et al., 2008). Ice extent (green) used as input for the inversion.

Table 3.2: List of parameters and a range of values varied in the result

Parameters		Tested values					Units
c	Max accumulation rate	0.25	0.5	<u>1.0</u>	2.0		myr ⁻¹
β	Mass balance gradient	0.0015	<u>0.004</u>	0.007	0.01	0.015	a ⁻¹
A	Deformation parameter	$0.25 \cdot A$	<u>A</u>	$3 \cdot A$			Pa ⁻³ s ⁻¹
f_s	Sliding parameter	$0.25 \cdot f_s$	<u>f_s</u>	$3 \cdot f_s$			Pa ⁻³ m ² s ⁻¹
Γ	Constriction factor	500	<u>2000</u>	4000			
T_e	Elastic thickness	10	<u>30</u>	50			km
E_0	Initial guess	<u>1400</u>	1900				m
n_{sm}	Number of diffusion iter	40	<u>400</u>	4000			
τ_1	Inversion update param	<u>45</u>	500				m
τ_2	Diffusion update param	$0.1 \cdot dy^2$	<u>$0.25 \cdot dy^2$</u>				m ²

3.4 Results

In this section, we report inversion results for 25 different scenarios. To investigate the robustness of the solution, we explore the parameter space of both the inverse and the forward model parameters. Below, four categories of experiments are presented. We vary (1) the climate variables, (2) the inverse model parameters, (3) the ice flow parameters and (4) the geodynamic properties. To investigate the role of climate, we vary parameters defining the mass balance rate, i.e., the maximum accumulation rate c (Fig. 3.2) and the mass balance gradient β (Fig. 3.3). For the inverse parameters, we test the influence of the initial guess on the solution (Fig. 3.4), the influence of smoothing (Figs. 3.5A and 3.5B) through the update parameters, i.e., τ_1 and τ_2 (Figs. 3.5C and 3.5D). To assess the role of ice mechanics, we vary the deformation parameter A (Figs. 3.6A and 3.6B), maximum value for the sliding parameter A_s (Figs. 3.6C and 3.6D) and the constriction factor Γ (Figs. 3.6E and 3.6F). Finally, the influence of geodynamic properties is investigated by varying the elastic thickness (Fig. 3.7) as well as the effect of bedrock topography (Fig. 3.8). Parameters kept constant in all scenarios can be found in Table 4.1. The list of parameters and the range of tested values can be found in Table 2. The underlined values in Table 4.2 are used unless stated differently in the text. Note that only one parameter is varied at a time.

A common feature in our results is a clear W-E gradient in ELA from the Lyon region to the east of Traun. The N-S gradient is less clear, it is more pronounced in the west (Solothurn lobe - Durance glacier) and the center of the Alps (Rhine glacier - Garda glacier), while in the east (Traun glacier - Drau glacier) it cannot be seen. In the center of the Alps, the gradient is tilted going from NW to SE, from the Rhine glacier towards the broader Garda glacier. In all scenarios, the ELA may be overestimated in the SW region of the ice extent where it is significantly higher than in the rest of the mountain range, due to complex topography in the region and our simple approximation of the ice flow.

Figure 3.2: Influence of the maximum accumulation rate c on the modeled ELA field. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent. (A) $c = 0.25$ m/yr, (B) $c = 0.5$ m/yr, (C) $c = 1.0$ m/yr, (D) $c = 2.0$ m/yr.

3.4.1 Sensitivity to climate (mass balance rate parameters: β , c)

To investigate the role of climate in our model (Eq. (A1)), we vary the maximum accumulation rate, c , and the mass balance gradient, β . The initial ELA for all of the scenarios within this subsection is set to 1400 m. If not varied in the scenario, β was set to 0.004 a^{-1} and c was set to 0.5 m/yr. All the results took 1000 inverse model iterations, except for scenarios presented in Figs. 3.2A and 3.2B where it took 750 and 900 iterations, respectively.

The maximum accumulation rate, c , corresponds to the maximum amount of ice accumulated within a year. A larger value for c prescribes wetter conditions over the Alps, while a lower c means a more arid climate (Eq. (A1)). Fig. 3.2 depicts the inversion model results for scenarios with different c , 0.25 m/yr (Fig. 3.2A), 0.5 m/yr (Fig. 3.2B), 1.0 m/yr (Fig. 3.2C) and 2.0 m/yr (Fig. 3.2D). Higher values for c have not been tested as they would imply significantly wetter conditions than reported for the Alps during the LGM (Peyron et al. 1998; Cohen et al. 2017). Fig. 3.2 shows that the ELA rises as c increases. This is because a larger c leads to thicker ice and therefore a more elevated ice surface and a larger ice cap. By raising the ELA , the ablation zone is enlarged and the modeled ice extent fits the observations.

The results reveal a W-E gradient in ELA , ranging from 1000 m - 1550 m in the west near Lyon to 1650 m - 2000 m east of Traun and north of Drau. In the central part of the Alps the N-S gradient in ELA ranges from about 1120 m - 1500 m near the Rhine glacier to 1500 m - 2150 m in the broader Garda region. In the west the N-S gradient (Solothurn lobe - Durance glacier) is more pronounced, ranging from 1350 m - 1500 m in the north to 1750 m - 2000 m near the Durance glacier and a maximum values of 2200 m - 2450 m in the southernmost part of the Alps.

We investigate the role of the mass balance gradient β for values ranging from 0.0015 to 0.015 a^{-1} (Table 4.2). The results are shown in Figure 3. The position of the ELA decreases as β increases. This is because β not only determines the elevation above ELA at which the mass balance rate reaches the maximum accumulation value c (Eq. (A1)), but also has a strong control on the rate at which the glacier ablates. A lower β means a gradual change in b with altitude, and corresponds to dry (sub)arctic conditions, while a higher β implies a steep change in b and corresponds to extreme maritime climate conditions (Oerlemans and Fortuin 1992). Reported drier conditions over the Alps during the LGM (Peyron et al. 1998; Florineth and Schlüchter 2000) would favour lower β values. The W-E and N-S gradients in ELA discussed above remain regardless of the β used (Figs. 3.3 and 3.2B (β 0.004 a^{-1})).

3.4.2 Sensitivity to the inverse model parameters

We investigate the influence of the inverse model parameters on the inversion results by changing the initial guess (Fig. 3.4), smoothing n_{sm} (Figs. 3.5A and 3.5B) and the update parameters, τ_1 and τ_2 (Figs. 3.5C and 3.5D).

The influence of the initial guess E_0 , i.e., the initial value of the ELA , is tested in two climate scenarios (Fig. 3.4). For each climate scenario, results are presented for two different initial guess values, 1400 m and 1900 m. In the first case (Scenario A) the maximum accumulation rate, c , was set to 1 m/yr and β to 0.004 a^{-1} (3.4A and 3.4B), while in the second case (Scenario B) c was set to 0.5 m/yr and β to 0.01 a^{-1} (Figs. 3.4C and 3.4D). Both scenarios show very small or no influence of the initial guess on the result. While Figs. 3.4A and 3.4B show no difference in the resulting ELA fields, Figs. 3.4C and 3.4D show small local differences in ice cover between two scenarios with the described gradients remaining.

The influence of the number of diffusion iterations, which control the amount of smoothing in the resulting ELA field, is visualized in Figs. 3.5A and 3.5B. We present two end-member scenarios with 40 and 4000 iterations. A small number of iterations fits the edges of the ice extent more precisely, introducing local variations to the ELA field (Fig. 3.5A). A large number of iterations removes the local variations. In all results the W-E and the N-S gradients in the ELA field (Fig. 3.5B) are preserved. This indicates that the two major gradients in the ELA field do not emerge due to local phenomena.

Figure 3.3: Influence of the mass balance gradient β on the modeled E field. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent. (A) β is set to 0.0015 a^{-1} , (B) β is set to 0.007 a^{-1} , (C) β is set to 0.01 a^{-1} , (D) β is set to 0.015 a^{-1} .

Figure 3.4: Modeled *ELA* fields for different initial guesses of the *ELA* for Scenario A and B described in section 4.2. (A) Scenario A with initial guess set to 1400 m, (B) Scenario A with initial guess set to 1900 m, (C) Scenario B with initial guess set to 1400 m, (D) Scenario B with initial guess set to 1900 m. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent.

Figure 3.5: Influence of smoothing on the modeled *ELA* field. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent. (A) Number of smoothing iterations is set to 40. (B) number of smoothing iterations is set to 4000, (C) τ_1 is set to 500, (D) τ_2 is set to 0.01 dy^2 .

The inversion update parameters τ_1 , the amplitude of the *ELA* update, and τ_2 , the amplitude of the applied smoothing, also influence the variance of the resulting *ELA* field. A large τ_1 , i.e., 500 (Fig. 3.5C), leads to large variations in *ELA* on the edges of the ice extent, overemphasising local variations. Note that these differences are maintained during the iterative process, which prevents the algorithm to converge. A result for τ_1 much smaller than the standard value of 45 is not presented because very small changes in *ELA* between two iterations do not lead to a difference in the resulting ice extent. A smaller value of τ_2 , set to 0.1dy^2 (Fig. 3.5D), reduces the influence of smoothing between two iterations, this in turn increases the number of iterations for the inverse model to converge. Besides changing the value of inverse parameters, the scenarios presented in Fig. 3.5 are the same as in Fig. 3.4A (c set to 1 m/yr and β to 0.004 a^{-1}).

3.4.3 Sensitivity to ice mechanics (deformation parameter, sliding parameter, constriction factor)

The tested ice mechanics scenarios consist of varying the deformation parameter A (Table 4.1), between $0.25A$ and $3A$ (Figs. 3.6A and 3.6B), the sliding parameter A_s , between $0.25A_s$ and $3A_s$ (Figs. 3.6C and 3.6D) and the constriction factor Γ , between 500 and 4000 (Figs. 3.6E and 3.6F). The initial *ELA* for each of the scenarios was 1900 m, β was set to 0.004 a^{-1} and c was set to 1 m/yr . Results for this scenario but with underlined values from Table 4.2 used for A , A_s and Γ are depicted in Fig. 3.2C. It is important to keep in mind that the SIA forward model is not solving a full set of Stokes equations and is only a rough approximation of ice flow. This implies that the complete parameter space and the role of ice mechanics is not fully explored here. The objective is simply to test the robustness of the inversion results, and seek for common characteristics between inversion results. Presented results took 1000 inverse model iterations, except for scenarios presented in Figs. 3.6C and 3.6D where it took 600 iterations.

First, we test the role of the deformation factor on the solution. In Figs. 3.6A and 3.6B, we show the solutions for different A values. Reducing the deformation parameter leads to thicker ice, which leads to a higher *ELA*. Figs. 3.6C and 3.6D show the results for varying the maximum value of the sliding parameter. While we varied deformation and sliding parameters in the same way, one quarter and three times the values used in Fig. 3.2C, Fig. 3.6 shows that the inversion result is significantly more sensitive to changes of the deformation parameter than the sliding parameter. The role of the constriction factor is investigated in Figs. 3.6E and 3.6F, showing little to no change in the results (Fig. 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Influence of ice mechanics on the modeled ELA field. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent. (A) Value of A is 0.25 times smaller than reported in Table 4.1 (B) value of A is three times larger than reported in Table 4.1 (C) Maximum value of A_s is 0.25 times smaller than reported in Table 1, (D) Maximum value of A_s is three times larger than reported in Table 4.1, (E) Γ is set to 500, (F) Γ is set to 4000.

Figure 3.7: Influence of elastic thickness T_e on the modeled ELA field. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent. (a) T_e is set to 10 km, (b) T_e is set to 50 km.

3.4.4 Sensitivity to elastic thickness

To investigate the role of flexure we vary the elastic thickness T_e . Although it is known that the elastic thickness under the Alps varies in space (Mey et al., 2016) we keep it spatially uniform and test two end member scenarios for $T_e = 10$ km and $T_e = 50$ km. The initial guess for the ELA for both scenarios was 1900 m, β was set to 0.004 a^{-1} and c was set to 1 m/yr. Fig. 3.7 shows negligible differences between the two solutions. It seems that on this scale, the change in elastic thickness does not influence the Alpine ice cap enough to change the final result of the inversion.

3.4.5 Sensitivity to bedrock topography

Finally, we test the influence of bedrock topography on the inversion results. To test this we use a bedrock topography with removed post-LGM valley fills created by Mey et al. (2016). The setup is the same as for Fig. 3.2C, with an initial guess of 1400 m, β set to 0.004 a^{-1} and c set to 1 m/yr. Fig. 3.8 shows no difference between this result and the ones using present day topography as bedrock. The calculated ice thickness is higher in the areas where the sediment has been removed but that does not influence the ice surface, therefore not changing the result significantly. This implies that our method can yield useful information on past environments even when applied to present-day topography.

3.5 Discussion

The aim of this paper is to estimate the mass balance rate in the Alps during the LGM and how it varies in space using the inverse method described in Višnjević et al. (2018). We report a series of inverse results that highlight spatial variations in the position of the

Figure 3.8: Influence of bedrock topography on the modeled *ELA* field. Bedrock from [Mey et al. \(2016\)](#) was used in the presented scenario. Results are presented where there is ice, bedrock elevation is depicted in gray, white outline represents mapped LGM extent.

equilibrium line altitude (*ELA*), and thus mass balance rate. To evaluate the robustness of our results, we ran a series of experiments in which we test the influence of the mass balance parameters, the inverse parameters, the ice dynamics, the flexural rigidity and variations in bedrock topography on the inferred equilibrium line altitude.

The most robust feature we observe is the presence of a W-E gradient in *ELA* across the Alps, with the position of the equilibrium line raising eastward. Such a gradient may imply higher precipitation in the western parts of the Alps compared to the east. As the air is lifted across the Alps, the air dries out and the equilibrium line altitude raises. Such an eastward flow supports the idea of zonal circulation-dominated conditions during the LGM ([Peyron et al., 1998](#)), and therefore precludes the idea of having meridional-dominated precipitation during the LGM ([Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000](#)). Interestingly, the need for a W-E gradient in the position of the equilibrium line altitude was also found by a recent and independent study ([Seguinot et al., 2018](#)), in which the authors modeled the transient evolution of the Alpine ice cap over a full glacial cycle (120-0 ka).

The second feature common to most inversion results is the presence of a N-S gradient in the western and central Alps, with the equilibrium line altitude rising from north to south, that is contrasted with the absence of a N-S gradient in the eastern Alps. One may think that the N-S gradient observed simply results from a temperature increase towards lower latitudes. However, assuming a standard latitudinal temperature lapse rate of 0.7°C per 1° of latitude ([La Sorte et al., 2014](#)) and a $6.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{km}$ *ELA* lapse rate ([Kuhlemann et al., 2008](#)) suggests a difference in equilibrium line altitude across the LGM ice cap of about 240 m in the central Alps and of about 340 m in the western Alps. The gradient predicted by our

inversion in the western and central Alps is systematically larger; ~ 400 m in the center and between 360 and 510 m in the west. Therefore, we speculate that other mechanisms than latitudinal temperature gradients must be invoked. In the western and central Alps, the inferred enhanced N-S gradient may be explained by an orographic precipitation pattern, i.e. higher precipitation rates on the northern flanks of the Alps compared to the south. Such a precipitation pattern would again imply zonal circulation-dominated conditions. Explaining the absence of a N-S gradient in the eastern Alps is, however, more complicated, and could be reflecting the influence of local conditions, such as strongly enhanced precipitation in the Tagliamento region and the north Adriatic sea, as can be seen in the present day annual precipitation pattern (Isotta and others, 2014; Mey et al., 2016, Supplementary Figure 5). A local increase in precipitation in the SE would lead to a regionally lower *ELA*, obscuring the N-S gradient in the eastern Alps.

Our approach does not enable us to constrain the absolute position of the equilibrium line altitude. The equilibrium line altitude depends on both precipitation and temperature (Ohmura et al., 1992), which cannot be disentangled using the ice extent alone. While changes in temperature primarily lead to changes in the position of the equilibrium line altitude (e.g., Oerlemans, 1997), changes in precipitation and humidity are primarily reflected by changes in the maximum accumulation rate c and the mass balance rate gradient β . An increase in the maximum accumulation rate c means an increase in precipitation rate, while an increase in β reflects an increase in humidity (Oerlemans and Fortuin 1992; Ohmura et al., 1992). Higher accumulation rates generate thicker ice caps and higher ice fluxes, with the implication that a higher c requires a higher equilibrium line altitudes for the same ice extent (Fig. 3.2). In contrast, increasing β induces larger ablation rates (Fig. 3.3), which must be compensated by a lowering of the equilibrium line altitude. As a result, large variations can be observed in the position of the equilibrium line altitude depending on the choice of c and β . Although, low c and β would correspond to drier conditions during the LGM, as suggested by field studies (Peyron et al., 1998), they can unfortunately not be constrained directly.

A clear limitation of our study is the assumption of spatially uniform c and β , so any spatial variations in precipitation will be reflected by a change in the position of the equilibrium line altitude. Recently, Mey et al. (2016) used a spatially variable c calibrated using modern annual precipitation data. Although the model predicts similar equilibrium line altitude patterns to ours, differences in absolute values can easily be explained by different c and β . Similarly, Becker et al. (2016) used a steady state model but included a reduction in precipitation north of the weather divide to reproduce the observed LGM ice extent, which they interpreted to reflect a reduction in precipitation rate on the northern flanks of the Alps due to a southward shift of the dominating storm track. However, they did not investigate how the equilibrium line altitude varies from west to east, which is one of our main findings.

Another limitation of our study is the steady state assumption of the ice extent at the LGM. Seguinot et al. (2018) argued that the LGM extent was a transient stage, concluding that there was a disequilibrium between glaciers and climate throughout the period. This implies that the timing of extent could be different in the north compared to the south. Unfortunately, we do not know how far the LGM climate was from the steady state assumption, while uncertainties of available dating techniques make it difficult to precisely identify asynchronous ice extents in time and space. In our model, it takes only about 1000 years for the ice cap to grow to the observed LGM extent and closely approach a climatic steady state. In a theoretical study Herman et al. (2018) report response times of a glacier on a similar time scale. These response times to climatic perturbations are shorter than the duration of the LGM (Clark et al. 2009). Furthermore, we observe large LGM moraines at the glacier outlets, implying longer periods of stability. For these reasons, it seems possible that the Alpine ice cap was in its position and close to steady state during most of the LGM.

Compared to the present day ELA with a mean of around 3000 m (Huss et al. 2008), our reconstructions show an overall decrease of about 1200 m to 1700 m for the LGM. Assuming that the change in equilibrium line altitude is solely due to temperature and using the same temperature - ELA relation as above, we arrive at a temperature depression of 7.8°C - 11°C, which falls in the range of values reported from modeling studies (Jost et al. 2005; Kageyama et al. 2006), compared to $12 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ mean annual temperature depression inferred from pollen (Peyron et al. 1998). This would imply a strong temperature control on the equilibrium line altitude. These results, however, must be treated with caution, as temperature cannot be determined independently.

3.6 Conclusion

We reconstructed the spatially variable altitude of the equilibrium line over the Alps during the LGM, following the inverse modelling approach described in Višnjević et al. (2018). Ice extent data from Ehlers et al. (2011) and a DEM of the Alps are used as input data for the model. We have conducted sensitivity tests for both the inverse and forward model parameters. Our model can reproduce the mapped LGM ice extent for a range of climatic scenarios, resulting in different *ELA* fields but keeping a distinct spatial pattern. The modeled *ELA* fields of the Alps are dominated by a W-E gradient, regardless of the chosen scenario. A pronounced N-S gradient can also be observed across scenarios in the central and western part of the mountain range. However, the absence of a pronounced N-S gradient in *ELA* over the entire Alps precludes the hypothesis of a southward shift of the westerlies during the LGM.

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CHAPTER 4

Constraining temperature and precipitation changes during the Last Glacial maximum in Europe from past ice extents

Vjeran Višnjević¹, Frédéric Herman¹, Günther Prasicek²

¹Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne

²Interdisciplinary Center for Mountain Research, University of Lausanne

Abstract

During the pinnacle of the last glacial period 20 kyr ago, the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), the Alps and the Pyrenees were covered by ice. Climate was colder and most likely drier. However, the magnitude of temperature and precipitation changes remain poorly constrained. This is in part because of the lack of accurate climate proxy, and because there are unknowns regarding the position of the westerlies during the LGM and, consequently, the dominating direction of the storm track and moisture flow towards Europe during that time of Earth history. Here we use a new inverse method and mapped ice extents to reconstruct the spatially variable position of the Equilibrium Line Altitudes (ELAs) in the Alps and the Pyrenees to gain insights into past climate. Using this approach, we can infer climatic patterns over the region and estimate the associated temperature change compared to today. We find that the mean temperature change for the tested scenarios from the LGM to present day is $\sim 9.3 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ in the Alps and $\sim 6.6 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ in the Pyrenees, which is less than suggested by pollen-based temperature reconstructions ($12 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$). We do not find any evidence for a southward shift of westerlies during glacial periods. We show that within the error range of reported temperature values, one can reproduce the mapped ice extents using vastly different precipitation rates. Our modeling results can only be reconciled with pollen-based reconstruction if climate was significantly drier ($>25\%$) during the LGM. Our findings help to further constrain the climate conditions in central Europe during that period.

4.1 Introduction

The last glacial period, peaking at the last glacial maximum (LGM) 24 ka ago, represents the most extensive period of glaciations in Earth’s recent history (Clark et al., 2009). Although many studies investigated the conditions in Europe during the LGM (Peyron et al., 1998; Kageyama et al., 2006; Ramstein et al., 2007; Bartlein et al., 2011; Strandberg et al., 2011), the influence of glaciations on the regional atmospheric circulation over the region is still poorly known (Kageyama et al., 2006; Allen et al., 2008a, b; Laîné et al., 2009; Hofer et al., 2012). How the expansion of the Fennoscandian ice sheet and the resulting southward expansion of the polar front influence the position of the Westerly winds and thus the dominant direction of the storm track is a topic of debate (Florineth and Schlüchter 2000; Luetscher et al., 2015; Monegato et al., 2017).

One of the main issues is the reported discrepancies in the mean annual temperature change reconstructions between pollen data and modeling studies (Jost et al., 2005; Ramstein et al., 2007). Pollen studies inferred a temperature anomaly of about $12 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ and a decrease in mean annual precipitation by $60 \pm 20\%$ (Peyron et al., 1998), while Beyerle et al. (1998), using a multitracer study, deduced that the temperature reduced during the LGM by at least 5°C . Modeling studies using atmosphere-ocean coupled models report $5\text{-}10^\circ\text{C}$ cooler conditions (Strandberg et al., 2011) and forward ice flow modeling suggests temperature anomalies of around 15°C (Allen et al., 2008b).

To address the large differences in reported change in Mean Annual Temperature (ΔMAT) since the LGM, we recently developed a new inverse method to reconstruct the position of the spatially variable ELA over a mountain range using ice extent data (Višnjević et al., 2018). ELAs provide invaluable information on past climate. Here we run 35 inversions in the Alps and 26 in the Pyrenees to estimate the range of possible temperature and precipitation rates that can explain the observed ice extents.

4.2 Methods

The method explained in Višnjević et al. (2018) and Višnjević et al. (in review) gives us the opportunity to analyze spatial patterns in the position of the ELA and recover information about climate conditions and the patterns of the dominating atmospheric circulation on a regional scale. We use an ice flow model based on the Shallow Ice Approximation (SIA) and assume a linear mass balance rate M :

$$b = \min(\beta(S(x, y) - E(x, y)), c), \quad (\text{A1})$$

Figure 4.1: Scheme depicting the influence of precipitation on mass balance parameters of an ice cap. Higher precipitation (wet conditions) increases the accumulation zone and lower the ELA. High balance gradient increases the ablation and raises the ELA.

where S is the ice surface, ELA is the position of the equilibrium line altitude, β is the mass balance gradient and c is the maximum accumulation rate. The ice flow model is run iteratively until a spatially varying ELA field is found that enables the modelled steady state ice cap to fit the observed ice extent, assuming synchronous development of the end moraines. Since inverting ice extent data for a spatially variable ELA field is an undetermined problem, we regularize it by assuming a smooth solution (Višnjević et al., 2018 Tikhonov regularization). We then apply the method to an ensemble of scenarios, varying climate, ice dynamics, inverse model and geodynamics parameters. As data, we use the mapped LGM ice extents for the Alps and the Pyrenees (Ehlers et al., 2011) and model ice flow on the present-day topography (Jarvis and others, 2008).

4.3 Results

We reconstruct the ELA for 36 scenarios for the Alps (25 from Višnjević et al. (in review) and 10 new ones; Appendix Table A2), as well as 27 scenarios for the Pyrenees (Appendix Table A3). As shown in Višnjević et al. (in review), one can reproduce the observed ice extents for a wide range of climate scenarios, many of them with vastly different implications on the climatic conditions over the region. However, in the case of the Alps, a common feature for

all of the reconstructed scenarios is a dominating W-E gradient, as well as the N-S gradient in the western and central Alps (Figure 2) (Višnjević et al. in review). The N-S gradient in the western and central Alps can be due to the temperature change caused by the latitudinal difference combined with more precipitation in the north than the south. The lack of a N-S gradient in the east can be explained with a high precipitation area in the SE part of the Alps, corresponding to what is observed in the present-day mean annual precipitation maps (Isotta and others, 2014; Mey et al. 2016, Supplementary Figure 5). High precipitation in this area would lead to a regional increase in ice production lowering the ELA and making the N-S gradient in the east indistinguishable. The W-E gradient across the Alps, with lower ELA values in the west and higher in the east, indicates the effect of moisture delivered by the Westerly winds, supporting the dominating zonal atmospheric circulation over central Europe during the LGM (Figure 2, blue arrow).

Figure 4.2: Reconstructed ELA in the Alps and Pyrenees using the inversion method introduced by Višnjević et al. (2018). The blue arrow depicts zonal dominated wind conditions, comparable to today's, and the red arrow depicts latitudinal dominated wind conditions, which would be induced by a southward shift of westerly winds (Florineth and Schlüchter 2000).

In the Pyrenees, we observe a clear N-S (NW-SE) gradient in the ELA in all inversion results (Fig. 4.2). Lower ELA values on the northern side of the mountain range indicate larger accumulation zones in the north compared to the south, which is caused by the precipitation brought by the Westerly winds from the Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 4.2, blue arrow). Additionally, by analyzing the mapped ice cover distribution over the mountain range, one can see that the unglaciated mountain tops, with accompanying unglaciated valleys, on the southern side

are higher or of equal height than the glaciated mountain tops and glaciated valleys on the northern side. If one assumes that the Westerly winds have shifted southwards during the LGM (Fig. 4.2, red arrow), the ELA pattern over the Pyrenees should be reversed, with large accumulation zones and lower ELA in the south instead of the north. In that case, the valleys on the southern side of the Pyrenees would experience more extensive glaciations than suggested by the observed ice extent.

To continue the analysis of our inversion results, we estimate temperature and precipitation conditions at selected locations; Mer de Glace and Aletsch glacier in the Alps and Ossue glacier in the Pyrenees (Fig. 4.1). We first compute the difference in ELAs between today and the LGM that we convert into a temperature difference assuming that a 100 m ELA difference (ΔELA) corresponds to 0.65°C change in temperature, following Kuhlemann et al. (2008). We repeat the calculations for a range of β and c (Eq. A1). The difference in precipitation is simply taken as the difference between c and the currently observed winter accumulation rate (M_w).

We find a mean temperature change equal to $9.3 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ at the Aletsch glacier, $8.6 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ at the Mer de Glace, $8.0 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ Silvretta Gletscher, and $6.6 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ at the Ossue glacier in the Pyrenees. Interestingly, our results replicate temperature variations reported in Bartlein et al. (2011) and fall within the range of previous atmosphere-ocean coupled models (Strandberg et al., 2011). In contrast, our results imply lower temperature anomalies than found using forward ice flow modeling (Allen et al., 2008a). In the case of the Alps (Figs. 4.3A and 4.3C), several scenarios can reproduce observations within the temperature range derived from pollen (Peyron et al., 1998), while we find lower temperature differences in the Pyrenees (Fig. 4.3D).

We cannot constrain precipitation rates during the LGM from the inversion results alone. The best correspondence between ice extent inversion results and pollen-based reconstructed temperature corresponds to dry conditions, i.e., at least 25% drier than today. It is therefore likely that this time of Europe's history was characterized by a dry, cold and inhospitable climate, which may be due to cold winds funnelling between the Fennoscandian ice-sheet and alpine icecaps.

4.4 Conclusions

We ran 63 inversions of past ice extents observed in the Alps and the Pyrenees to constrain climate in Europe during the LGM. We find a W-E gradient in the position of the ELA in the Alps and a N-S gradient in the Pyrenees suggesting that wind directions were most likely not that different from today. We also find the temperature differences were about 9°C in

Figure 4.3: Inverted temperature difference between the LGM and present day for glaciers in the Alps and the Pyrenees. A) the Aletsch glacier (Huss et al., 2008, $ELA_{\text{present}} = 3003 \text{ m}$, $M_w = 1.14 \text{ m.w.e.a}^{-1}$), B) the Mer de Glace (Viani et al., 2018, $ELA_{\text{present}} = 2880 \text{ m}$, $M_w = 1.71 \text{ m.w.e.a}^{-1}$) and C) the Silvretta glacier (Huss et al., 2008, $ELA_{\text{present}} = 2811 \text{ m}$, $M_w = 1.19 \text{ m.w.e.a}^{-1}$), and D) the Glacier de Ossue in the Pyrenees (Mélières and Maréchal, 2015, $ELA_{\text{present}} = 3000 \text{ m}$). Vertical dashed line represents the present-day winter mass balance (M_w). In the case of the Pyrenees $M_w = 2.81 \text{ m.w.e.a}^{-1}$ (Marti et al., 2015). Violet line represents the mean and the range of temperature change reconstructed by pollen (Peyron et al., 1998), while yellow line represents the multitracer study reconstruction by Beyerle et al. (1998). Horizontal black line represents the mean value, and horizontal dashed lines represent the standard deviation scenarios presented in this study. Colorbar represents the β value used in the scenario.

the Alps and 6°C in the Pyrenees and that climate must have been at least 25% drier to reproduce temperature depressions reported by pollen studies.

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4.5 Appendix

Figure 4.4: Inverted temperature difference between the LGM and present day for glaciers in the Alps and the Pyrenees. A) the Aletsch glacier (Huss et al., 2008, ELA_{present} = 3003 m, $M_w = 1.14$ m.w.e.a $^{-1}$), B) the Mer de Glace (Viani et al., 2018, ELA_{present} = 2880 m, $M_w = 1.71$ m.w.e.a $^{-1}$) and C) the Silvretta glacier (Huss et al., 2008, ELA_{present} = 2811 m, $M_w = 1.19$ m.w.e.a $^{-1}$), and D) the Glacier de Ossue in the Pyrenees (Mélières and Maréchal, 2015, ELA_{present} = 3000 m). Vertical dashed line represents the present-day winter mass balance (M_w). In the case of the Pyrenees $M_w = 2.81$ m.w.e.a $^{-1}$ (Marti et al., 2015). Violet line represents the mean and the range of temperature change reconstructed by pollen (Peyron et al., 1998), while yellow line represents the multitracer study reconstruction by Beyerle et al. (1998). Horizontal black line represents the mean value, and horizontal dashed lines represent the standard deviation scenarios presented in this study. Color bar represents the β value used in the scenario. Error bars represent different lapse rates used; top bar - 100 m ELA = 0.85°C, circles - 100 m ELA = 0.65°C, bottom bar - 100 m ELA = 0.5°C

Table 4.1: *Forward model parameter values kept constant in all scenarios*

Constant	Value	Units
N	Max number of inverse iterations	1000
n_{xAlps}	Number of points in x (Alps)	1024
n_{yAlps}	Number of points in y (Alps)	1024
n_{xPyr}	Number of points in x (Pyrenees)	512
n_{yPyr}	Number of points in y (Pyrenees)	512
dx_{Alps}	Spatial resolution in x (Alps)	784.5 m
dy_{Alps}	Spatial resolution in y (Alps)	568.4 m
dx_{Pyr}	Spatial resolution in x (Pyrenees)	674.6 m
dy_{Pyr}	Spatial resolution in y (Pyrenees)	324.1 m
A_0	Ice-flow parameter	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-24}$ Pa $^{-3}$ s $^{-1}$
f_s	Sliding flow parameter	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-20}$ Pa $^{-3}$ m 2 s $^{-1}$
ρ	Ice density	910 kgm $^{-3}$
g	Gravitational constant	9.81 m 2 s $^{-1}$
n	Exponent in Glen flow law	3
c_{stab}	Time step coefficient	0.1235
yr	Seconds per year	31556926 s
q	Surface heat flow	$70 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mWm $^{-2}$
k	Thermal conductivity of underlying bedrock	2.35 Wm $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$
$(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z})_S$	surface temperature gradient	0.005 °C/m
κ	Thermal diffusivity of ice	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m 2 s $^{-1}$
ρ_a	Asthenosphere density	3300 kgm $^{-3}$
ν	Poisson's ratio	0.25
Y_m	Young's module	$100 \cdot 10^9$ Pa

Table 4.2: *Table A2. Modeled scenarios: Alps*

	c [myr ⁻¹]	β [a ⁻¹]	A [Pa ⁻³ s ⁻¹]	A _s [Pa ⁻³ m ² s ⁻¹]	Γ	Te [km]	N _{sm}	τ_1	τ_2	Init. Guess [m]
1	0.25	0.0015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
2	0.25	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
3	0.25	0.01	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
4	0.25	0.015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
5	0.25	0.02	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
6	0.5	0.0015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
7	0.5	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
8	0.5	0.007	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
9	0.5	0.01	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
10	0.5	0.015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
11	0.5	0.02	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
12	1.0	0.0015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
13	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
14	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	500	0.25·dy ²	1400
15	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	10	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
16	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	50	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
17	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.1·dy ²	1400
18	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	500	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
19	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	4000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
20	1.0	0.004	A ₀	0.25·f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
21	1.0	0.004	A ₀	3.0·f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
22	1.0	0.004	0.25·A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
23	1.0	0.004	3.0·A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
24	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	40	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
25	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	4000	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
26	1.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1900
27	1.0	0.015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
28	1.0	0.02	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
29	1.5	0.0015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
30	1.5	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
31	1.5	0.01	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
32	1.5	0.02	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
33	2.0	0.0015	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
34	2.0	0.004	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
35	2.0	0.007	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400
36	2.0	0.02	A ₀	f _s	2000	30	400	45	0.25·dy ²	1400

Table 4.3: *Table A2. Modeled scenarios: Alps*

	c	β	A	A_s	Γ	Te	N_{sm}	τ_1	τ_2	Init. Guess
	[myr ⁻¹]	[a ⁻¹]	[Pa ⁻³ s ⁻¹]	[Pa ⁻³ m ² s ⁻¹]		[km]				[m]
1	0.25	0.0015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
2	0.25	0.004	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
3	0.25	0.01	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
4	0.25	0.02	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
5	0.5	0.0015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
6	0.5	0.004	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
7	0.5	0.004	$3.0 \cdot A_0$	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
8	0.5	0.007	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
9	0.5	0.01	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
10	0.5	0.01	$3.0 \cdot A_0$	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
11	0.5	0.02	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
12	1.0	0.0015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
13	1.0	0.004	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
14	1.0	0.004	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
15	1.0	0.004	$3.0 \cdot A_0$	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
16	1.0	0.007	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
17	1.0	0.01	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
18	1.0	0.015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
19	1.0	0.02	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
20	1.5	0.0015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
21	1.5	0.01	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
22	1.5	0.02	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
23	2.0	0.0015	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
24	2.0	0.004	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
25	2.0	0.01	$3.0 \cdot A_0$	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
26	2.0	0.01	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900
27	2.0	0.02	A_0	f_s	2000	25	100	45	$0.25 \cdot dy^2$	1900

CHAPTER 5

General Conclusion

The primary aim of this thesis is to develop and apply a simple inversion method in order to reconstruct the spatially variable mass balance rate and equilibrium line altitude (ELA) fields across a mountain range using ice extent, or ice thickness, data. In Chapter 1, I present a range of applications of the inverse method and apply it to synthetic and real data examples. This approach offers the possibility of constraining past climates in glaciated mountain ranges, and enables us to investigate the dominant directions of atmospheric circulations on a regional scale. The inverse method is based on a Tikhonov regularization, assuming a smooth solution, and additionally to the forward model only requires an extra calculation of a diffusion equation, making it easy to implement, and has already been implemented in other fields as well (Jelinski et al., 2019). To significantly reduce the calculation time necessary for our inverse model, as well as solving high resolution problems on the scale of a mountain range, we have implemented the codes to run on GPUs. The main advantage of our approach is that our inversion algorithm works as a spatially variable optimization.

In Chapter 2, I have applied the method to reconstruct the spatially variable altitude of the ELA over the Alps during the LGM, following the inverse modelling approach described in Chapter 1 (Višnjević et al., 2018), and using ice extent data from Ehlers et al. (2011) and a DEM of the Alps as model input (Jarvis and others, 2008). Since inverting for ice extent does not lead to a unique solution I have conducted a range of sensitivity tests for both the inverse and forward model parameters, showing that the method can reproduce the mapped LGM ice extent for a range of climatic scenarios. Different scenario reconstructions have different ELA fields but all of them have in common a distinct spatial pattern. All of the results for the Alps are dominated by a clear W-E gradient, regardless of the chosen scenario, and exhibit a pronounced N-S gradient in the central and western part of the mountain range. The W-E gradient across the Alps has lower ELA values in the west and higher in the east, indicating to the effect of moisture delivered by the Westerly winds, thus supporting the dominating zonal atmospheric circulation over central Europe during the LGM. Yet, the lack of a N-S gradient in the east can be explained with a high precipitation area in the SE part of the Alps, corresponding to what can be seen in the present-day mean annual precipitation maps (Isotta and others, 2014; Mey et al., 2016, Supplementary Figure 5), which would lead to a local increase in ice production lowering the ELA and making the N-S gradient in the east indistinguishable. However, the absence of a pronounced N-S gradient in ELA over the entire Alps precludes the hypothesis of a southward shift of the Westerlies during the LGM.

In case of the Pyrenees (Chapter 3), the results of the reconstruction show a clear N-S (NW-SE) gradient in the ELA, with lower ELA values on the northern side of the mountain range pointing to larger accumulation zones in the north compared to the south. This recovered pattern in the ELA indicates to the precipitation brought by the Westerly winds from the Atlantic Ocean. Additionally, by analyzing the mapped ice cover distribution over the mountain range, one can see that the unglaciated mountain tops, with accompanying unglaciated

valleys, on the southern side are higher or of equal height than the glaciated mountain tops and glaciated valleys on the northern side. In the case of the southern shift of the Westerlies, one would expect that the valleys on the southern side of the Pyrenees would experience more extensive glaciations than suggested by the observed ice extent.

Finally, I ran 63 inversions of past ice extents observed in the Alps and the Pyrenees to constrain climate in Europe during the LGM. I have chosen to focus my analysis on the mountain ranges of the Alps and the Pyrenees because they are influenced by the same regional circulation, thus looking at them as a system can help us to better understand the governing climate conditions during the LGM. My findings are that the W-E gradient in the position of the ELA in the Alps and a N-S gradient in the Pyrenees suggest that the wind directions were most likely not that different from today. Additionally, I also find that the temperature differences were about 9°C in the Alps and 6°C in the Pyrenees and that climate must have been at least 25% drier to reproduce temperature depressions reported by pollen studies (Chapter 3). It is therefore likely that this time of Europe's history was characterized by a dry, cold and inhospitable climate, which may be due to cold winds funneling between the Fennoscandian ice-sheet and alpine icecaps.

CHAPTER 6

Perspectives

I have presented the newly developed inverse method to reconstruct the spatially variable ELA across the mountain chain using ice extent or ice thickness data as model input. In this chapter I will discuss the research perspectives and propose the next steps in development of this method but also of the described approach to gain insights into paleoclimate conditions.

6.1 Research perspectives

In this manuscript I have presented the possibilities of the newly developed inverse method to investigate paleoclimatic variations on a regional scale, such as the influence of the Westerlies on the position of the ELA (Chapter 1) or using the method to gain insight into dominant regional circulation patterns (Chapters 2 and 3), as well as in combination with field observations and other proxies to constrain temperature and precipitation changes since present-day. Supported by the presented results, the spatial variability this approach can retrieve shows potential to be applied to previously glaciated regions across the globe, from investigating the influence of the Westerlies in Patagonia and New Zealand during the LGM to investigating the position of the storm track and temperature change across North America or Asia by reconstructing ice extents of ice caps across the continent.

Since the change in ELA can be translated into the change in temperature and precipitation (Kerschner et al., 2000), it is possible to constrain the precipitation by knowing the temperature field, and vice versa, from other proxies, e.g. pollen. Combining these approaches would open a possibility to reconstruct the spatial variability of temperature and precipitation fields for a certain period. Such reconstructions would be valuable input for atmospheric models and other reconstructions, as well as crucial information to resolve the climate conditions on a regional scale.

Such analysis is not constrained to only one time period. A transient inversion could be attempted in a case where one has good constraints on the position and the age of the ice extent over several time slices. This is often not the case due to the large error bars on the moraine ages (Wirsig et al., 2016). One can, instead of a transient simulation, perform this analysis on the same mountain range in different time slices, treating each time slice as its own independent inversion. The approach presented in this manuscript can easily be expanded to such analysis, and applied to a well-preserved moraine system. All of this points to a high potential of the glacial component in paleoclimatic studies and enables an opportunity to use ice flow model to reconstruct the change in temperature and precipitation, as well as patterns of regional climate in combination with other proxy data, but also give valuable insights into past climate in areas where we do not have an abundance of other data.

6.1.1 Method perspectives

One of the main lackings of the presented approach is the inability to properly quantify errors within the method. The main issue at the moment is time needed to calculate large enough number of inverse model runs in order to be able to apply standard statistic practices. This is due to the amount of time it takes for a single inversion run, because of the large number and computation time of forward model iterations, within the inversion. The problem needs

to be tackled by improving the convergence of the method, reducing the number of forward models needed, and by adapting the codes to run on multiple graphic cards (MPI).

The convergence of the method can be increased by combining different data within the inversion, e.g. combining ice extent and ice thickness data, where possible. By combining ice extent data with the ice thickness data, one will not only increase convergence but also better constrain the reconstructed values inside of the ice cap, not only on the edges. Additionally, convergence can be increased by choosing a more appropriate misfit function within the inversion algorithm. For example, instead of calculating differences between the modeled and observed ice extents and then diffusing the update from the edges towards the inside of the ice cap, one could propagate the update along the flowline. This would increase the updated area within one iteration, and potentially significantly reduce the number of forward model iterations needed within the inversion run to converge.

Additionally, method advances can be achieved by increasing the computational efficiency of the codes and developing the potential to run the inversion on multiple graphic cards (GPUs) in parallel (MPI). Computing on multiple GPUs enables splitting the computational domain in smaller and faster to calculate pieces, opening the opportunity to apply the method to large regions, e.g. Patagonia and larger, without sacrificing resolution or computation time. This would open a possibility to fully explore the parameter space with a simpler model, constrain the solution, and then use the retrieved climate information as input for a detailed transient or steady state simulation using a higher order model, e.g. ISSM or PISM. Such approach would enable going from mapped moraines, and ice thickness points if available, to fully constraining glacial history of an area, thus retrieving invaluable paleoclimatic information in areas and time periods where the data coverage is sparse.

Finally, the method can be used to invert other ice flow or climate parameters, and even applied to fields other than glaciology and paleoclimate. As shown in Chapter 1, the method is fully capable of inverting the mass balance gradient field instead of the ELA, as well as use ice thickness data instead of the ice extent data as input. One can impose different mass balance rate formulations and use the method to recover a different unknown field, but also use values as ice velocity or similar as additional constraints. The method has already been applied in a different field, where the authors [Jelinski et al. \(2019\)](#) modified it to reconstruct paleo-surfaces in a study where they use meteoric Beryllium-10 as a tracer of erosion.

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Curriculum vitae

Education

- Ph.D., University of Lausanne, 2019 (no defence date yet).
 - *Thesis title* Reconstructing climate patterns in Europe during the LGM from inversions of past ice extents
 - *Committee* Prof. Dr. Christian Kull, Prof. Dr. Frééric Herman
Prof. Dr. Jean Braun, Prof. Dr. Yury Podladchikov
Dr. Guillaume Jovet
- Master's degree Physics-Geophysics, Module - Seismology and physics of solid earth
Department of Geophysics, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Croatia, 2013.
- Bachelor in Geophysics, University of Zagreb, Croatia, 2010.
- High school, Mathematical Gymnasium, Bjelovar, Croatia 2005.

Professional Experiences

- Geophysics Intern at the "Fund for Financing the Decommissioning of the Krško Nuclear Power", Zagreb, Croatia, 2014
- Data analysis in Medicine, 2010 - 2014
Institute for Research and Development of the Sustainable Eco Systems, Zagreb, Croatia

Fields of Research Interest

Glacier climate interactions, Paleoclimate, Earth system modeling, Numerical modeling, Inverse methods, GPU programming

Selected Scientific Publications

- Visnjevic V, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2018). Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modelling *Journal of Glaciology*
Višnjević, V., Herman, F. and Prasicek G. (in review) Climatic patterns over the European Alps during the LGM derived from inversion of the paleo-ice extent. *Earth and Planetary Surface Letters*.
- Višnjević, V., Herman, F. and Prasicek G. (in review) Constraining temperature and precipitation changes during the Last Glacial maximum in Europe from past ice extents. *Geology*.
- Duverger A., Herman F., King G.E., Valla P.G., Lehmann B., Visnjevic V. and Cox S.C. (in review). Glacial erosion during a glacial cycle: insights from the Franz Josef Glacier/Ka Roimata o Hine Hukatere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface: Earth Surface*

Memberships and awards

- Rector's reward, University of Zagreb, Croatia, 2012

Teaching Experience

- BSc, Tectonic, Erosion Climate, Unil, 2017.
- BSc, Numerical Modelling, Unil, 2016-2018.
- Ms, Initiation Matlab, Unil, 2017.

Publication list

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F., Podladchikov Y. (2018). Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modelling *Journal of Glaciology*
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F., Prasicek G. (in review). Climatic patterns over the European Alps during the LGM derived from inversion of the paleo-ice extent *Earth and Planetary Surface Letters*
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F., Prasicek G. (in review). Constraining temperature and precipitation changes during the Last Glacial maximum in Europe from past ice extents *Geology*
- Duverger, A., Herman, F., King, G.E., Valla, P.G., Lehmann, B., **Visnjevic V.** and Cox S.C. (in review). Glacial erosion during a glacial cycle: insights from the Franz Josef Glacier/Ka Roimata o Hine Hukatere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface: Earth Surface*

Invited talks

- Climatic patterns over the Alps and the Pyrenees during the LGM derived from inversion of the paleo-ice extents (Invited seminar)
May 2019 at VAW, ETHZ, Zurich, Switzerland

- Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents (Monique lecture)
June 2018 at University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland
- Inverse problems: Simple application of Tikhonov optimization method (Monique lecture)
July 2017 at GFZ, Potsdam, Germany

Conference participations

- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y., Prasicek G. (2019) Poster. Reconstructing spatially variable Equilibrium Line Altitude over the Alps and Pyrenees during the LGM. European Geosciences Union, Vienne, Austria.
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2018) Poster. Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents. American Geosciences Union 2018, Washington DC, USA.
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2018) Talk. Reconstructing glacier mass balance over a mountain range using Octopus. Swiss Geocomputing Centre kick-off workshop, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2018) Talk. Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents. European Geosciences Union, Vienne, Austria
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2017) Poster. Reconstruction of past equilibrium line altitude using ice extent data. European Geosciences Union, Vienne, Austria
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2016) Talk. Glacier climate interaction: reconstruction of the mass balance field using ice extent data. Swiss Geosciences Meeting, Geneva, Switzerland
- **Visnjevic V.**, Herman F, Podladchikov Y. (2016) Poster. Insight into glacier climate interaction: reconstruction of the mass balance field using ice extent data. European Geosciences Union, Vienne, Austria

CHAPTER 7

Publications

7.1 Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modeling

Vjeran Višnjević¹, Frédéric Herman¹, Yury Podladchikov²

¹ Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, 1012, Switzerland.

² Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, 1012, Switzerland.

Research paper

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Author contributions. VV designed the study, wrote the ice flow model with FM and implemented the codes for GPU, created the experiments, ran simulations and wrote most of the manuscript. All authors contributed in interpreting the results and improving the text.

Reconstructing spatially variable mass balances from past ice extents by inverse modeling

VJERAN VIŠNJEVIĆ,¹ FRÉDÉRIC HERMAN,¹ YURY PODLADCHIKOV²

¹Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

²Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

Correspondence: Vjeran Višnjević <vjeran.visnjevic@unil.ch>

ABSTRACT. With the conclusion of the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), about 20 000 years ago, ended the most recent long-lasting cold phase in Earth history. This last glacial advance left a strong observable imprint on the landscape, such as moraines, trimlines and other glacial geomorphic features. These features reflect the extent of former glaciers and ice caps, which in turn provides information on past temperature and precipitation conditions. Here we present an inverse approach to reconstruct the equilibrium line altitudes (E) from observed ice extents. The ice-flow model is developed solving the mass conservation equation using the shallow ice approximation and implemented using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs). We present the theoretical basis of the inversion method, which relies on a Tikhonov regularization, and demonstrate its ability to constrain spatial variations in mass balance with idealized and real glaciers.

KEYWORDS: ice and climate, ice-sheet mass balance, mass-balance reconstruction, moraine

1. INTRODUCTION

The Quaternary period, spanning the last 2.6 million years of Earth history, was marked by warm and short interludes between long and cold periods. While literature provides tight constraints on how climate varied during glacial periods in marine settings (Zachos and others, 2001; Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005; Herbert and others, 2016), changes in temperature and precipitation on continents remain poorly constrained. Use and availability of proxies such as pollen (Peyron and others, 1998) and speleothems (Luetscher and others, 2015) can help shed more light on past climate conditions. However, past glacial advances have left a strong imprint on the Earth's surface in the form of moraines, trimlines and other glacial geomorphic features, which provide us invaluable information on past climate on continents (Penck, 1905; Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Laabs and Carson, 2005). Furthermore, thanks to geochronological methods (Gosse and Phillips, 2001), such as ^{14}C (Hajdas, 2009), cosmogenic nuclide (Blanckenburg and Willenbring, 2014) and optically stimulated luminescence dating (Rhodes, 2011), the timing of past glacial advances can be dated.

Ice-flow models have been used before to infer past climate conditions on continents (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Anderson and others, 2006; Kessler and others, 2006; Jouvét and others, 2008; Golledge and others, 2012; Rowan and others, 2014; Eaves and others, 2016; Mey and others, 2016). These studies consisted of running ice-flow models forward and fitting observed moraines by optimizing some of the model parameters. A key component in such models is the mass balance, which defines ice accumulation and ablation, and is thus primarily a function of precipitation and temperature (Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). Several models exist to simulate mass balance, from the simple positive degree-day model (Braithwaite, 1995) to more sophisticated energy mass-balance models (Oerlemans, 1992, 1997; Becker and others, 2016; Pellicciotti and others, 2016). These models have been successfully applied to reconstruct

glacial history (Becker and others, 2016; Seguinot and others, 2018), but require knowledge of a large number of uncertain parameters, which might change over a glacial cycle. In-depth analysis of ice-flow models used for paleoclimatic reconstructions can be found in the paper by Kirchner and others (2016).

In practice, past ice thicknesses are poorly constrained. Recent studies on the European Alps have emphasized the systematic mismatch between paleo ice-flow model and reconstruction from trimlines (e.g., Cohen and others, 2017; Seguinot and others, 2018), in terms of ice thickness. Here we introduce an inversion method to infer spatially varying mass-balance information from the former extent of glaciers derived from geomorphological observations, such as moraines. We apply a gradient descent method to minimize a cost function, which includes the misfit between modeled and geomorphological maximal glacial extents and a regularization term to ensure sufficient smoothness of the inverted variables. As a result, the method consists of running a forward model a large number of times with a tuning of the mass balance at each iteration. The ice-flow model is modeled by solving the mass conservation equation using the shallow ice approximation (SIA) (Mahaffy, 1976; Hutter, 1983) and the developed codes are accelerated using Graphic Processing Units (GPUs).

Below, we first introduce the basic equations governing our forward model. Then we present the theoretical basis behind the method and provide a step-by-step recipe for its numerical implementation. We then illustrate the method's efficiency for constraining spatial variations in mass balance over mountain ranges with a series of examples.

2. FORWARD MODEL

2.1. Ice dynamics

At the time scale relevant for ice-sheet dynamics, ice can be described as a viscous and incompressible non-Newtonian

fluid (Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). Ice thickness can be modeled by solving the mass conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + b, \quad (1)$$

where H is the ice thickness, \mathbf{q} is the horizontal ice flux and b represents the mass-balance rate. Horizontal ice flux is defined as vertically integrated velocity field $\mathbf{q} = \int_B^S \mathbf{u} dz$, and we approximate velocities using the SIA:

$$\mathbf{u}(z) = \underbrace{-A(\rho g)^n [H^{n+1} + (S-z)^{n+1}] |\nabla S|^{n-1} \nabla S}_{(i)} + \underbrace{A_s(\rho g)^n H^{n-1} |\nabla S|^{n-1} \nabla S}_{(ii)}, \quad (2)$$

where (i) represents the deformation velocity and (ii) represents the sliding velocity, S is the surface altitude, ρ is density of ice, g is the gravitational acceleration, A is the ice-flow parameter, A_s is a sliding parameter and n is the Glen flow law exponent. Values for the flow parameters A and A_s are taken from Oerlemans (1997) (who used values from Budd and others (1979)), and can be found listed in Table 1, along with the other parameter values used in the model.

The SIA is based on the assumption that large ice bodies are mainly deformed by vertical shear stress, and therefore neglects longitudinal stresses in the mass conservation equation (Eqn 1). We are using this approximation with the assumption that the horizontal scale of the ice extent is much larger than the vertical scale ($H \ll L$). Solving of full set of Stokes equations, a full set of momentum equations, would give more realistic results (especially near the margin and ice divide). However, the ice extent is primarily a function of mass balance, topography and ice dynamics. Since we only consider the extent of ice as forward model output in our inversion method, we restrict our analysis to the SIA.

The mass-balance rate, b , is defined as the annual gain, accumulation, or loss of mass, ablation, at the glacier surface (e.g., Oerlemans, 2001; Cuffey and Paterson, 2010). We define the mass-balance rate, b , as a spatially varying variable:

$$b = \min(\beta(S(x, y) - E(x, y)), c), \quad (3)$$

where β is the balance rate gradient, E is the equilibrium line altitude (i.e., the location where accumulation is equal to ablation) and c is a maximum ice accumulation rate (e.g., Meier, 1962; Kessler and others, 2006; Oerlemans, 2008). The evolution of the ice cap or glacier surface is in part determined by the mass-balance rate and its values depend on the local climate conditions. Mass-balance rate is positive in the accumulation area and negative in the

Table 1. Ice-flow model parameters

	Constants	Value	Units
A	Ice-flow parameter	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$\text{Pa}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
A_s	Sliding flow parameter	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-20}$	$\text{Pa}^{-3} \text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ	Ice density	910	kgm^{-3}
g	Gravitational constant	9.81	ms^{-2}
n	Exponent in Glen flow law	3	

ablation area. The mass-balance gradient, β , tends to be steeper in the ablation than accumulation area (Mayo, 1984). To keep the problem simple for introducing the inversion method, we choose the balance gradient to be constant.

Solving Eqn (1) using the SIA (Mahaffy, 1976; Hutter, 1983) leads to a non-linear diffusion-reaction type equation that can be solved numerically (Hindmarsh and Payne, 1996). In that case, the ice flux \mathbf{q} is defined as

$$\mathbf{q} = -D\nabla S, \quad S = H + B, \quad (4)$$

where B is the bedrock and D is the diffusivity expressed as:

$$D = (\rho g)^n [AH^{n+2} + A_s H^n] |\nabla S|^{(n-1)}. \quad (5)$$

The main advantage of models based on using SIA to solve the mass conservation equation Eqn (1) is their computational efficiency, which we further enhance using GPUs. The details of the numerical implementation we use can be found in the Appendix A. Note, however, that the inversion method approach we propose can be used with other types of approximations for ice flow, such as solving a full set of Stokes equations or a higher order approximation of these equations (e.g., Pattyn, 2003; Egholm and others, 2011), as long as it is computationally possible. For the moment, running 1000–3000 inversion model runs with higher order models without the use of GPUs is not practical.

3. INVERSION METHOD

In this section, we provide the theoretical basis of the inversion method and its numerical implementation.

3.1. Theoretical basis

Our objective is to invert a known ice extent into a spatially variable E using the forward model explained in Section 2. The forward problem is defined as:

$$h_m(x, y) = F(E(x, y), \beta), \quad (6)$$

where $h_m(x, y)$ is the data we are trying to fit (note that $h(x, y)$ is used for ice extent and $H(x, y)$ for ice thickness), F is the forward model (the ice-flow model), and $E(x, y)$ and β are the unknown parameters of the mass-balance equation, Eqn (3), we wish to constrain. Below we derive the method to infer $E(x, y)$ and show it can be extended to β .

As with any inversion method, the primary objective is to minimize the misfit between the model predictions and the observations. To do so, we define a misfit function $G(E)$ as a spatially integrated difference between the ice extent calculated for a forward model, $h_m(x, y)$, and the observations, $h_o(x, y)$ as:

$$G(E) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))^2 dx dy, \quad (7)$$

where $[0, L_x] \times [0, L_y]$ is our computational domain. The chosen computational domain strictly contains the area where thickness is positive, i.e., we have $S = B$ in the neighborhood of the border of the domain. The goal is then to minimize the misfit function G by varying $E(x, y)$ iteratively.

We now look for a descent direction to define a sequence of E_i , which minimizes the misfit function G . For that purpose, we formally compute $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$, the directional

derivative of G with respect to E along a given direction δE :

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = - \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} \delta E dx dy. \quad (8)$$

The term $\partial h_m / \partial E$ represents the change of ice extent with respect to E , which are both function of x and y .

The goal of the inversion is to minimize G , and thus make $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$ negative. However, the inverse problem is under-determined (Hansen, 1994; Zhang and Xu, 2011). We solve this by imposing some form of regularization. Here we assume a smooth solution and impose smoothness on E using a Tikhonov regularization (Tikhonov, 1963; Poplavskii and others, 2001). We do this by defining a new misfit function G , now containing the regularization term:

$$G(E) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[\underbrace{(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))^2}_{(i)} + \tau_2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \right] dx dy, \quad (9)$$

(i) in Eqn (9) is the same as in Eqn (7), while (ii) imposes the smoothness on the solution. The parameter τ_2 is a positive constant which acts as the additional constraint of smoothness. A large constant would force the solution to be very smooth, while a small or zero constant would cancel this constraint. Following the same derivation as above for (ii):

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta E}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta E}{\partial y} \right) dx dy, \quad (10)$$

and using the integration by parts:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \delta E}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \delta E}{\partial y} \right] dx dy \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial y} \right) \delta E \right]_{0,0}^{L_x, L_y} - \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} \delta E + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \delta E \right) dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Because the first term on the right-hand side becomes negligible, as there is no ice on the boundaries of the model, we can choose E in the neighborhood of the border such that $\partial E / \partial x = \partial E / \partial y = 0$, so $\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle$ becomes:

$$\langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle = \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[-\tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta E dx dy, \quad (12)$$

which combined with Eqn (8) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle &= \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(-\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta E dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Following the same logic, one can perform the same development for β instead of E :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle G'(\beta), \delta \beta \rangle &= \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \left(-\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial \beta} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial y^2} \right) \right] \delta \beta dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

3.2. Numerical implementation of the inverse algorithm

To this end, we use the gradient descent method (Press, 2007; Fletcher, 2013), in which $E(x, y)$ is updated with the following increment:

$$\delta E = - \left[\tau_1 (h_o - h_m) - \tau_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial y^2} \right) \right]. \quad (15)$$

This choice of δE leads to a decrease of the misfit G , assuming an appropriate choice of the iteration parameters τ_1 and τ_2 , which are positive constants. We show below that recombining and substituting Eqn (15) into Eqn (13) results in negative increment of the misfit G :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle &= \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \left[-\delta E - (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \left(\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} + \tau_1 \right) \right] \delta E dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Sorting Eqn (16) leads to:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle G'(E), \delta E \rangle &= - \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} [\delta E]^2 dx dy \\ &\quad - \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} (h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y)) \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{\partial h_m(x, y)}{\partial E} + \tau_1 \right) \delta E dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Table 2. Implementation of the inversion algorithm

Inversion algorithm	
I.	Assign initial guesses for E
II.	Run the forward SIA model $F(E, \beta)$, mass-balance rate b is calculated using (Eqn (2)).
III.	Output of the forward model, the ice extent (h), is used to calculate an error function γ : $\gamma = h_o - h_m$
IV.	Update the E by multiplying the error function γ with accompanying parameters: $E = E - \tau_1 \gamma$
V.	The problem is regularized by applying diffusion to updated E $E = E + \tau_2 \nabla^2 E$
VI.	Repeat steps II to V until γ is minimized

One can see that Eqn (18) is negative if the term $(h_o(x, y) - h_m(x, y))$ is sufficiently small, in other words the method converges if our initial guess is not too far from the final solution.

In practice, we follow the steps of the inversion algorithm presented in Table 2. First, we start by assigning an initial guess for E (step I). We arbitrarily choose an equilibrium line altitude field, E , and add some white noise to avoid imposing a spatial pattern to the solution, and therefore avoid the influence of the initial guess on the solution. Adding random noise enables to test whether the method can retrieve a meaningful solution or not, even with a poor initial guess. Next, the mass conservation equation Eqn (1) is solved using the mass-balance rate field, (b) , calculated using the input E , Eqn (3), and the model is run until a steady state is reached, i.e., the ice thickness and ice extent do not change (step II). The output of the forward model, i.e., the ice extent, is used to calculate γ (step III). We define γ as the difference between observed ice extent data and ice extent calculated from a forward model run. Note that although the algorithm works using ice thickness (H), we rarely know it. In that case, we calculate ice extent (h) by setting ice thickness equal to 1 where there is ice, and equal to 0 where there is no ice. Step IV consists of updating the equilibrium line altitude locally by increasing (or decreasing) it where the modeled ice extent/ice thickness was found large (or small). If the glacier is too thick or goes beyond the ice extent, E is raised. Conversely, E is lowered if the glacier extent is too small. We then regularize the problem by applying diffusion on E using τ_2 (step V) for a chosen number of diffusion iterations, n_{sm} . Steps IV and V correspond to one step of the descent direction given by Eqn (15). Finally, we return to step II, and iterate until γ is minimized (step VI). In the case where we want to invert for β instead of E , the described steps remain the same. One only needs to replace E with β in the equations since the equations are identical.

The parameters τ_1 and τ_2 are positive scalar values, which must be chosen. Both τ_1 and τ_2 are problem dependent. The choice is based mainly on the spatial dimensions of the problem and the spatial variability of the solution.

Furthermore, the choice of the inversion update parameter τ_1 reflects on the precision of the result. Too high a value will make it difficult for the inversion algorithm to converge to the solution because of too large jumps in value of E after each inversion step. On the other hand, a small value, after applying diffusion, might not result in a change in E that is sufficiently large enough to modify the ice extent of an area, thus not enable to fit the data successfully.

Diffusion in step V represents the smoothness one wishes to impose on E . We do this by iteratively solving the diffusion equation using a fully explicit scheme. The degree of smoothness is set by the number of iterations used in the explicit scheme. A large number of diffusion iterations may lead to a very smooth solution, and might not enable to capture local variations in mass-balance rate. In contrast, a small number of diffusion iterations leads to overfitting the data. We must keep in mind that we are fitting the ice extent by varying only one physical parameter, E , and that differences between observations and our model output could come also from the assumptions made in our forward model. The choice of number of diffusion iteration is illustrated later on.

We would like to stress here, the algorithm shows that the method only requires computing ice thickness and the Laplacian of E .

4. RESULTS

In this section, we illustrate the efficiency of the method with a series of synthetic examples. We start with a simple 2-D problem and then present a 2-D synthetic example using real topography (Uinta Mountains). In the simple 2-D example we show, in separate experiments, that the method can invert the ice extent in order to recover both E and β , while in the Uinta Mountains example we show that one can use ice thickness as well as ice extent to reconstruct E . Finally, we show how the method can be applied to a natural example at the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) in the South Island of New Zealand. In the following experiments, ice extents are presumed to be reached at the same time, steady state solution, and sliding is parametrized to be constant. The balance gradient, β , is also kept constant in all examples except where we use the method to recover β . Since we can only do our inversion in the area of the map where we have ice, the results will also be presented only within the ice extent.

4.1. Two-dimensional inversion

For this 2-D case, we present two experiments. First, we invert the synthetic ice extent and assess whether the method enables us to recover the prescribed E , and in the second experiment we show that the method is capable to recover β as well. The ice thickness, hence ice extent as well, are simulated by prescribing an arbitrary E and β .

A combination of two simple Gaussian shapes is used for the bedrock:

$$B = B_0 \left[\exp\left(-\frac{X^2}{10^{10}} - \frac{Y^2}{10^9}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{X^2}{10^9} - \frac{(Y - (L_y/8))^2}{10^{10}}\right) \right], \quad (18)$$

where B_0 is the maximum bedrock elevation, X and Y represent the matrices of distance vectors, and L_y is the length scale in the y -direction. The prescribed E_0 we wish to recover is defined as follows:

$$E_0 = 2150 + 900 \arctan\left(\frac{Y}{L_y}\right). \quad (19)$$

In this experiment, β is constant and set to 0.01. The initial guess is equal to 3000 m with 400 m amplitude white noise.

In the second experiment, we show that the method enables to recover the mass-balance gradient, β . For this, we use the same setup as above, i.e., bedrock is defined as in Eqn (18), and E as in Eqn (19). We prescribe β_0 we wish to recover:

$$\beta_0 = 0.01 + 0.015 \arctan\left(\frac{X}{L_x}\right), \quad (20)$$

where L_x is the length scale in the x -direction.

Figure 1 shows the calculated E and β (Figs 1a and 1c) and the differences between our inversions and the prescribed values (Figs 1b and 1d). In both cases, during the inversion, convergence is reached when the differences between the forward model output ice extent differ from our synthetic ‘observations’ by <10 points. The results show that convergence is reached after 293 iterations for E and 149 iterations for β . More importantly, the two results demonstrate that it is

Fig. 1. (a) shows the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (b) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the ice extent), (c) shows the calculated (modeled) β using our inversion algorithm, (d) difference between synthetic and calculated β where there is ice (within the ice extent).

possible to recover E and β using this approach, and capture the spatial variation that was imposed by Eqns (19) and (20) and illustrated in Figs 1a and 1c. The parameters used in this test are summarized in Table 3.

4.2. Two-dimensional inversion, Uinta Mountains synthetic test

Now the method is applied to a real topography. In this example, we show that the method is capable of restoring spatially variable E by using the ice extent as well as ice thickness as data. The Uinta Mountains, North America, was used as bedrock topography (Fig. 2a). The topography was extracted from the SRTM data (Jarvis and others, 2008) and smoothed using a median filter.

First, a forward model was run with a prescribed E_o , which includes some spatial variability. The imposed pattern follows a N-S arctangent form. The ice extent is derived from the calculated ice thickness, which then represents

the synthetic observations that we wish to invert for mass balance. The ice extent is calculated by setting the ice thickness equal to 1 where there is ice, and to 0 where there is not. Furthermore, high peaks that pierce through the ice are not included in our misfit calculations. The initial guess for E_m field is 3100 m with 400 m amplitude random white noise added to it. To assess the performance of the inversion scheme, the sum of differences between the synthetic E_o field and the calculated E_m are monitored. All parameters used can be found in Table 4.

The results of the inversion for the E_m field are represented and compared with the prescribed E_o field in Fig. 2b. The differences between the prescribed solution E_o and inversion model solution E_m are <30 m, which falls under 5% difference from the prescribed solution (Fig. 2c).

We now repeat the same test with the same forcing, but instead of using the ice extent we randomly chose ice thickness points on our synthetic glacier. Out of 40 317 ice thickness points within the ice extent we chose 433 (Fig. 9a). The only difference in the approach from the previous example is that now we calculate γ as a difference of ice thickness values in the chosen points between calculated and synthetic ice. The resulting figures (Fig. 9 in Appendix B) and tables with used parameters can be found in Appendix B.

Now we investigate the influence of the number of the diffusion iterations. We report two different end-member cases. The first one uses only five diffusion iterations (Fig. 3a) and the second uses 5000 iterations (Fig. 3b). Fig. 3 shows the differences between the E_o for the two end-member tests. It appears that the choice of the number of diffusion iterations strongly influences the precision of the result. A large number of diffusion iterations reduces the spatial variability in mass balance, and is thus filtering out any local gradient, whereas a small number of diffusion iterations reduces the rate at which the residuals are decreased (Fig. 4).

Table 3. Two-dimensional inversion parameters

	Constants	Value	Units
B_0	Max. bedrock elevation	3500	m
β	Mass-balance gradient	0.01	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	m a^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	100	
n_y	Number of points in y	100	
L_x	Length scale in x	250 000	m
L_y	Length scale in y	200 000	m
n_{sm}	Number of diffusion iterations (both cases)	30	
$\tau_1 (E)$	E inversion update parameter	390	m
$\tau_1 (\beta)$	β inversion update parameter	0.015	a^{-1}
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter (both cases)	$0.25 \cdot \min(dx^2, dy^2)$	m^2

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Fig. 2. (a) shows the bedrock map used (Uinta Mountains) with the synthetic ice extent, (b) is the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (c) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines extent).

4.3. Inversion of LGM ice extent in the South Island of New Zealand

To verify the method for a real situation, we reconstruct the LGM mass balance using the observed ice extent of the

Table 4. Uinta Mountains inversion experiment parameters

	Constants	Value	Units
β	Mass-balance gradient	0.007	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	512	
n_y	Number of points in y	512	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	339.56	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	242.44	m
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	150 000	
n_{iter}	Number inverse iterations	1000	
τ_1	E inversion update parameter	150	m^2
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter	14 336	m^2
n_{sm_1}	Number of diffusion iterations – Figure 4b	50	
n_{sm_2}	Number of diffusion iterations – Figure 5a	5	
n_{sm_3}	Number of diffusion iterations – Figure 5b	5000	

South Island of New Zealand (Barrell, 2011). This example offers us the possibility of comparing the results with previous reconstructions (Golledge and others, 2012).

The South Island's climate is heavily influenced by the Westerlies. As the air flows across the Southern Alps, precipitation is orographically enhanced with up to 10 m a^{-1} of precipitation on the west side (Henderson and Thompson, 1999). The eastern slopes see considerably lower rates of precipitation (about 1 m a^{-1}) as a consequence of the westerly airflow across the mountain range.

In the past, the Southern Alps have experienced extensive glaciations, including full transitions from glacial to fluvial processes (Whitehouse, 1988). Climate has controlled the growth and decay of mountain glaciers in New Zealand since at least 2.4–2.6 Ma (Suggate, 1990), as testified by an exceptional moraine record across the entire South Island (Barrell, 2011). During the LGM, the North Atlantic meridional overturning circulation was weakened compared with present, the Intertropical Convergence Zone shifted southward, which in the southern mid-latitudes modified the location of wind and temperature (Rojas and others, 2009; Denton and others, 2010; McGlone and others, 2010). The LGM was thus marked by changes in regional atmospheric conditions that affected winds and precipitation in the Southern Alps, which may have led to a change in humidity, possibly up to 25% drier than today (Golledge and others, 2012). Temperatures were between 4°C and 8°C lower than today (Newnham and others, 1989; Barrows and others, 2007; Golledge and others, 2012; Seltzer and others, 2015). Most importantly, despite these changes, the orographically enhanced precipitation was preserved during the LGM. This contrast of precipitation is also observed in the position of the equilibrium line altitude, E , on either side of the mountain range (Golledge and others, 2012). Therefore, the spatial variation in E provides us with an appropriate test.

In this inversion, we constrain $E(x, y)$ using the LGM ice extent (Barrell, 2011) shown in Fig. 5a. For simplicity, we use the present day bedrock with all elevations below sea level set to zero. Note, we assume that the ice extent obtained from data is reached at the same time over its entire length. All parameter values used for this test can be found in Table 5.

We present two model results, test A and test B, for two different sets of τ_1 , τ_2 and n_{sm} . Both test results (Fig. 5) exhibit a clear north–south gradient in the elevation of E , as well as the west–east gradient. The N–S change could be the result of the temperature change because of the latitudinal differences, making the southern areas colder and with larger accumulation zones, and in turn lower E values. The W–E gradient reflects the influence of the westerly winds bringing precipitation to the west side, thus increasing the accumulation and lowering the altitude of E , while the east side is drier with less accumulation and higher E .

In the second test, test B, we reduce the values of the update parameters, τ_1 and τ_2 , and the number of diffusion steps n_{sm} . Reducing n_{sm} leads to more local variations. Smaller τ_2 (five times smaller than the first test) reduces the influence of smoothing, while a smaller τ_1 results in smaller changes in E between iterations, all resulting in a more precise fit. Figs 6a and 6b show the differences between the observed (data) and calculated ice extent (model) for each test. Test B enables to better fit the data,

Fig. 3. (a) is the difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines ice extent) with number of diffusion iterations set to 5, (b) is the difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice with number diffusion of iterations set to 5000.

Table 5. New Zealand inversion experiment parameters

	Constants	Value	Units
β	Mass-balance gradient	0.02	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	1024	
n_y	Number of points in y	1024	
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	110 000	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	668.99	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	646.51	m
n_{iter}	Number inverse iterations	3000	
τ_{1_1}	E inversion update parameter - test A	100	m
τ_{2_1}	Diffusion update parameter - test A	101 944	m^2
n_{sm_1}	Number of diffusion iterations - test A	100	
τ_{1_2}	E inversion update parameter - test B	25	m
τ_{2_2}	Diffusion update parameter - test B	20 389	m^2
n_{sm_2}	Number of diffusion iterations - test B	5	

although it does it at the expense of creating local depressions in E . This information is lost in the first test because higher smoothing, n_{sm} , acts as a filter of local variations. It is worth keeping in mind that we are showing the results of the inversion algorithm varying only one parameter, E . This results in overfitting the data and neglecting the influence of other physical processes ignored in the model as well as approximations made in the forward model, as stated above.

Fig. 4. Residuals calculated as a sum of differences between the synthetic E and the calculated E where there is ice. The red dots represent residuals for the case shown in Figure 3a, green for case shown in Figure 3b and blue the case from Figure 2.

Fig. 5. Application of the inverse algorithm to the South Island of New Zealand. (a) Bedrock map used (gray) with the LGM ice extent obtained from Barrell (2011) (green), (b) calculated (modeled) E field using our inverse algorithm where there is ice (Test A), (c) E field calculated with the second set of parameters using our inverse algorithm where there is ice (Test B).

Fig. 6. Differences between the observed and modeled ice extents. (a) Test A. (b) Test B. Yellow represents areas where the data have ice but the model output does not, the red is where the model output calculates ice and the data show there was no ice in those areas.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this paper is to present a simple inversion method to reconstruct the spatially variable mass balance and equilibrium line altitude (E) fields using ice extent data. This approach offers the possibility of constraining past climates in glaciated mountain ranges. The inverse method is based on a Tikhonov regularization and computationally, besides the forward model, only requires the calculation of a diffusion equation. In order to show the range of applications of the method, we have constructed six experiments, both synthetic and natural, whose results are presented. To significantly reduce the calculation time necessary for our inverse model, we have implemented the codes to run on GPUs.

In the first experiment, the 2-D synthetic case, we have shown the method is capable of reconstructing a spatially variable E as well as a spatially variable β on a simple topography, consisting of a combination of two Gaussian bumps, using ice extent (Fig. 1). The second experiment is the 2-D synthetic case using real topography (Uinta Mountains) where we show that the method can successfully reconstruct spatially variable E , defined as an arctangent function from N–S, using only ice extent as constraint for our inversion. We first ran our forward ice-flow model with a chosen setup and then used the calculated ice extent as synthetic observations to invert E we originally used. The error while recovering E is less than 5% (Fig. 2c). The same was done in the experiment using ice thickness points presented in Appendix B. The difference is that instead of the ice extent we are using randomly chosen ice thickness points (Fig. 9a). Fig. 9 in Appendix B shows that the method can do the inversion successfully. When analyzing errors of the results obtained using ice extent (Fig. 2c) and ice thickness (Fig. 9c), we can see that using the ice extent the largest error is in the middle of the ice extent and the opposite effect using ice thickness. This happens because the method is more precise in places where it is better constrained by data. In the ice extent case, the errors are smaller on the edges, and in the ice thickness case, errors are larger on the edges and smaller inside the ice because of the distribution of our ice thickness points.

The influence of different number of diffusion iteration has been presented (Figs 3a, 3b). It is clear that too many diffusion iterations will result in losing the spatial variability of the result, while too little iterations will not propagate the update from the edges of the ice efficiently to its middle.

In order to verify the method, we applied it to a real case, the LGM ice extent of the South Island of New Zealand (Barrell, 2011). The assumption made in this experiment is that the entire ice extent is reached at the same time, representing something close to the LGM steady state. Our inversion result for the first test is similar in both pattern and values to the reconstruction done by other authors (Golledge and others, 2012). Fig. 5b shows a clear N–S gradient, which corresponds to the latitudinal change and is thus controlled by temperature, and a clear W–E gradient, which corresponds to the influence of the Westerlies and is thus controlled by precipitation. The second result is an example of overfitting the data. It is important to emphasize that the model setup for this experiment is simplified, which is one of the reasons for the mismatches between the observed and calculated ice extent (Fig. 6b). The bedrock topography used was the current one and the values below sea level were set to 0, thus ignoring calving. Basal sliding was parameterized as a constant value, while basal melting was not taken into account. The influence of isostasy was ignored, which is not a valid assumption for such an ice mass, and is most likely the reason E elevations are higher than expected. Despite these limitations, our method is still able to invert the spatial pattern, both the N–S and W–E gradients, and recover values close to other reconstructions.

The experiments presented show several possible applications. In order to obtain a more accurate reconstruction of mass-balance parameters for large mountain ranges, the forward model needs to be improved to include the effects of isostasy. The choice of bedrock topography for a certain time period remains a setback. The use of present day topography for LGM neglects the change in the amount, distribution and thickness of eroded and deposited sediments since the LGM. Sediment-filled valleys today might have been empty or not even eroded. This influences where our ice can flow in forward model calculations, changing the resulting ice extent and therefore our inverse calculations.

The role of β has not been fully addressed in cases where we attempt to recover E . In the presented experiments the balance gradient β was set to be constant value, and chosen arbitrarily. Future work will include an expansion of the method in order to recover both spatially variable E and β fields. Computationally, adding the inversion of another parameter in the algorithm would only

require the calculation of an additional diffusion equation for β .

Similar methods to quantify climate parameters (temperature, precipitation, mass balance, equilibrium line altitude) using ice extents have been developed by other authors (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Kessler and others, 2006; Golledge and others, 2012; Rowan and others, 2014). The approaches differ in defining the climate forcing (energy balance model, positive degree-day model, net mass balance Eqn (3)), and the ice-flow models used vary in complexity. Some authors use current day conditions or present-day mean annual temperature and precipitation measurements to produce scenarios where these parameters are uniformly changed, temperature reduction by -1°C or precipitation lowered by 25%, and then compare ice-flow model calculations with observations. The main difference with our approach is that our inversion algorithm works as a spatially variable optimization.

Overall, we show that by calculating only an additional diffusion equation, the method is capable to reproduce the general pattern of a spatially variable E over a mountain range using ice extent data.

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APPENDIX A. NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FORWARD MODEL

Equation (1) is solved explicitly using the finite difference method (FDM) on a staggered grid (Hindmarsh and Payne, 1996). Figure 7 is a schematic presentation of a staggered grid. The ice thickness points are in the nodes of the grid, while fluxes are in between the nodes and the diffusivities are in the middle of the cell. To conserve mass and avoid unrealistically large fluxes that can occur when using the SIA on high resolutions and steep terrains (Plummer and Phillips, 2003; Jarosch and others, 2013), we have

Fig. 7. Scheme representation of the staggered grid.

Fig. 8. Comparison between our numerical solution and the benchmark provided from Jarosch and others (2013). The red line represents the bedrock topography; the blue line is the analytical solution. The blue dots are the numerical solution of our forward model.

Fig. 7 - Colour online, Colour in print

Fig. 8 - Colour online, Colour in print

implemented a flux correction for diffusivity calculations based on an algorithm inspired by Wang and others (2011). This changes how B , H and the slope ∇S in Eqns (4) and (5) are calculated compared with Hindmarsh and Payne (1996) and substantially helps the convergence of our forward model. The topography and ice thickness are computed as follows:

$$\tilde{B}_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} = \max[B_{i,j}, B_{i+1,j}, B_{i,j+1}, B_{i+1,j+1}], \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\tilde{H}_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{4} \max[0, S_{i,j} - \tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j} - \tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1} - \tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1} - \tilde{B}], \quad (\text{A2})$$

and the slope:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial x} \approx \frac{\max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j}) + \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1})}{2dx}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial y} \approx \frac{\max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i,j}) + \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\tilde{B}, S_{i+1,j})}{2dy}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

and the squared norm:

$$|\nabla S|^2 = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial y}\right)^2. \quad (\text{A5})$$

Finally, the fluxes in x and y directions are defined as:

$$q_{x(i+\frac{1}{2},j)} = \frac{D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} + D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \frac{\max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i,j+1}), S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i,j+1}), S_{i,j+1})}{dx}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$q_{y(i,j+\frac{1}{2})} = \frac{D_{i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}} + D_{i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2}}}{2} \frac{\max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i+1,j}), S_{i+1,j+1}) - \max(\max(B_{i+1,j+1}, B_{i+1,j}), S_{i+1,j})}{dy}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Combining the above expressions gives us the divergence of the flux:

$$\nabla \cdot q \approx \frac{q_{x(i+\frac{1}{2},j)} - q_{x(i-\frac{1}{2},j)}}{dx} + \frac{q_{y(i,j+\frac{1}{2})} - q_{y(i,j-\frac{1}{2})}}{dy}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

Because we are solving our equations explicitly, our time step dt is strongly restricted by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition, resulting in many forward model iterations before converging to a solution. We balance this by writing our codes for GPUs, which significantly increase our computational efficiency. GPUs are specialized for intensive highly parallel computation (graphics rendering) with more transistors devoted to data processing rather than data caching and flow control (NVIDIA, 2017). Since we are only interested in steady-state solutions of Eqn (1), we accelerate the convergence using a local time step, such that

$$dt_{ij}^t = \min\left(\frac{1}{c}, c_{\text{stab}} \frac{\min(dx^2, dy^2)}{\epsilon + \tilde{D}_{ij}^t}\right), \quad (\text{A9})$$

where dx and dy is the spatial step, dt_{ij}^t is the local time at each iteration, c is the maximum ice accumulation rate

Table 6. Uinta Mountains ice thickness experiment

Constants		Value	Units
β	Mass-balance gradient	0.007	a^{-1}
c	Max. ice accumulation	2.0	ma^{-1}
n_x	Number of points in x	512	
n_y	Number of points in y	512	
dx	Spatial discretization in x	339.56	m
dy	Spatial discretization in y	242.44	m
n_t	Number of forward model iterations	150 000	
n_{iter}	Number inverse iterations	1000	
τ_1	E inversion update parameter	14	m
τ_2	Diffusion update parameter	11 712	m^2
n_{sm}	Number of diffusion iterations	130	

from Eqn (3), c_{stab} is the time-step coefficient (Courant number, for 2-D cases in this paper set to 1/8.1), ϵ is a small number (10^{-3}) and \tilde{D}_{ij}^t is the spatially averaged value of diffusivity for a given point (i, j) for the current (t) iteration. Note here that one can solve the steady-state solution of the reaction-diffusion equation directly as a non-linear elliptic equation (Jouvet and others, 2008, 2011; Jouvet and Bueler, 2012).

Because solving our inverse problem explicitly may require a large number of iterations, thousands of inverse model iterations and tens to hundreds of thousands forward model iterations, or if we are interested in either high-resolution or continental scale problems, we accelerate the code on GPUs using the parallel computing platform CUDA created by NVIDIA (Micikevicius, 2009; NVIDIA, 2017). Other authors have also implemented ice-flow models for GPUs (Brædstrup and others, 2014).

When implemented on GPU, the computation time for our forward model to calculate 110k iterations, and reach steady state, on a 1024×1024 grid takes around 113 s using GeForce GTX TITAN black card, and 76 s using TITAN X card, both cards were used to for our experiments and both are gaming cards, while one iteration step takes around 121 s and under 80 s, respectively. This number varies with the model of the GPU used. Just as an example

Fig. 9. Results of the inversion algorithm using ice thickness points instead of ice extent (a) position of the randomly chosen ice thickness points with color corresponding to their altitude (point size not to scale), (b) is the calculated (modeled) E using our inversion algorithm, (c) difference between synthetic and calculated E where there is ice (within the moraines extent).

to solve the same forward problem with the same setup on a professional GPU NVIDIA Tesla V100 takes 24 s. The forward model was benchmarked using the experiment proposed by Jarosch and others (2013) (Fig. 8).

APPENDIX B. UINTA EXAMPLE USING ICE THICKNESS

Here we present the result and the values used for the inversion experiment using ice thickness values instead of ice extent. Fig. 9a represents the result of the method, while Fig. 9b shows the differences between the calculated E and a synthetic one. Parameter values used in the setup can be found in Table 6.

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